

An International Conference

The [National Technical University of Athens](#) (Greece), [Jordan University of Science and Technology](#) (Jordan), [Politecnico di Torino](#) (Italy), [University of Cyprus](#), [McGill University](#) (Canada) and [Fuzhou University](#) (China), are organizing the 1st International Conference on Optimization-Driven Architectural Design ([OPTARCH2019](#)) to be held in Amman, Jordan from November 5th - 7th, 2019.

Supporting Organizations

[OPTARCH2019](#) is endorsed by:

[International Society for Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization \(ISSMO\)](#)

[European Council of Civil Engineers \(ECCE\)](#)

[Scientific Technical Chamber of Cyprus \(ETEK\)](#)

[Association of Civil Engineers of Greece \(ACEG\)](#)

[Cyprus Architects Association \(CAA\)](#)

Registration Fees

The [registration fees](#) are in Euros (United States Dollar). Early registration applicable if received before September 15th, 2019.

Type of participant	Early Registration	Late Registration
Delegate	500 € (572 \$)	600 € (686 \$)
Student	300 € (343 \$)	400 € (457 \$)
Accompanying persons	120 € (137 \$)	120 € (137 \$)

[Registration fees](#) include: A copy of conference proceedings, attendance at all scientific sessions of [OPTARCH2019](#), reception, coffee breaks, lunches and banquet.

Important Dates

Abstract Submission	25 th May 2019
Acceptance of the abstract	10 th June 2019
Deadline for early payment	15 th September 2019
Deadline for submitting the full paper (optional)	30 th November 2019
Acceptance of the full paper	30 th December 2019

Social Programme

The social programme for delegates will include a reception and a banquet at a local place of interest. The social programme will not be included in the reduced student fee.

Accompanying Persons Programme

The accompanying persons programme features a full-day excursion to the magnificent city of Amman sites of interest on the city.

OPTARCH2019
November 5th – 7th, 2019, Amman, Jordan

How to register and submit contributions

Authors are invited to submit their contributions on any of the conference topics. Submission of contributions and conference registration should be performed online via the conference web site <http://www.just.edu.jo/OptArch2019/Pages/default.asp> from the "Authors Area" and "Registration" menu correspondingly.

Conference Secretariat

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OPTARCH2019

1st International Conference on Optimization - Driven Architectural Design

November 5th – 7th, 2019, Amman, Jordan

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Objectives

The main objective of the [OPTARCH2019](#) Conference is to bring together the scientific community working in the broader field of Engineering Optimization and Architectural Design including problems formulation, computational methods and software development. OPTARCH conferences will facilitate the exchange of ideas in topics of mutual interests and will serve as a platform for establishing links between research groups with complementary activities. Thus, the communities of *Mathematical Programming* and *Nature-Inspired Search Algorithms* will become more familiar with important application areas arising from Architectural design real-world problems. Moreover, the *Architectural Design Community* will be exposed to advanced numerical methods and software tools, which can highly assist in tackling combinatorial optimization problems.

Sessions related to specific topics of the Conference will be introduced by Keynote Lectures which will be complemented by invited Minisymposia, organized by recognized experts in research areas of current interest, as well as by contributed papers.

Conference Topics

- ✓ Shape and topology optimization: topological derivatives, level set methods, isogeometry-based shape optimization, topometry and topography optimization, sensitivity analysis, etc.
- ✓ Linear, nonlinear, stochastic, parametric, discrete and dynamic programming – modelling.
- ✓ Optimization software.
- ✓ Evolutionary algorithms, swarm optimization, scatter search, etc.
- ✓ Parallel and distributed computing in optimization – Cloud computing, GPGPU computing environment.
- ✓ Theory of metaheuristics, landscape analysis, convergence, large neighborhoods, etc.
- ✓ Multiple criteria decision making and optimization.
- ✓ Local search, tabu search, simulated annealing, VNS, ILS, etc.
- ✓ Hybrid methods with metaheuristics, machine learning, game theory, mathematical programming, constraint programming, co-evolutionary, etc.
- ✓ Energy (energy harvesting, storage, delivery, efficiency, etc.), environment and climate.
- ✓ Artificial intelligence, surrogates-metamodels, fuzzy systems.
- ✓ Structural optimization: composite materials, transient loads and crash, fatigue and fracture, etc.
- ✓ Lifecycle design optimization and structural health monitoring.
- ✓ Multidisciplinary and multiphysics design optimization.
- ✓ Emergent nature inspired algorithms: quantum computing, artificial immune systems, DNA computing, etc.
- ✓ Design under uncertainty: robust design optimization, reliability based design optimization, theoretical foundations and framework.
- ✓ Optimization in emerging areas like micro- and nano-mechanics, multiscale, additive manufacturing.
- ✓ Generative and parametric design

Location

[Grand Millennium Amman hotel](#) is one of the most luxurious Convention Centres offering the latest in meeting technology. High standard materials, modern ideas and excellent space design - adopted and applied in order to achieve maximum comfort, prestige and splendour – **guarantee to make the conference a special event.**

About Amman

[Amman](#) has served as the modern and ancient capital of Jordan. It is one of the oldest continuously inhabited cities in the world, with a 1994 excavation uncovering homes and towers believed to have been built during the Stone Age, circa 7000 BCE. There are many Biblical references to the city, which by about 1200 BCE had become the Ammonite capital of Rabbath-Ammon. The Ammonites fought numerous wars with Saul, David and others. Amman is built on seven hills, or jabals, each of which more or less defines a neighborhood. Most jabals once had a traffic circle, and although most of these have now been replaced by traffic lights, Amman's geography is often described in reference to the eight circles which form the spine of the city. First Circle is located near downtown, and the series extends westward through Eighth Circle.

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Accommodation

Block reservations at reduced rates have been arranged at the conference hotel. Information on this hotel and its rates is available at the Conference website.

OPTARC-2019

Amman, Jordan
November 5th – 7th, 2019

1st International Conference on
Optimization-Driven Architectural Design

Book of Abstracts

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1st International Conference on Optimization-Driven Architectural Design: **Amman-Jordan, November 5th - 7th, 2019**

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Preface

The purpose of the Conference is to bring together the scientific community working in the broader field of Engineering Optimization and Architectural Design including problems formulation, computational methods and software development. OPTARCH2019 conferences will facilitate the exchange of ideas in topics of mutual interests and will serve as a platform for establishing links between research groups with complementary activities. Thus, the communities of Mathematical Programming and Nature-Inspired Search Algorithms will become more familiar with important application areas arising from Architectural design real-world problems. Moreover, the Architectural Design Community will be exposed to advanced numerical methods and software tools, which can highly assist in tackling combinatorial optimization problems.

The main objective of the OPTARCH2019 Conference is to bring together the scientific community working in the broader field of Engineering Optimization and Architectural Design including problems formulation, computational methods and software development. OPTARCH conferences will facilitate the exchange of ideas in topics of mutual interests and will serve as a platform for establishing links between research groups with complementary activities. Thus, the communities of Mathematical Programming and Nature-Inspired Search Algorithms will become more familiar with important application areas arising from Architectural design real-world problems. Moreover, the Architectural Design Community will be exposed to advanced numerical methods and software tools, which can highly assist in tackling combinatorial optimization problems.

The aim of the editors is to provide a valuable source for anyone interested in engineering optimization and architectural design, including students, researchers and practitioners from all areas of engineering and industry.

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1st International Conference on Optimization Driven Architectural Design

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MINI-SYMPOSIA

MS1: Bioclimatic Building Design Improvement through Performance Optimization

Organizers: Agni Kouvela (Couvelas Architects), Sotiria Inetzi (SHAPE Ltd)

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Bioclimatic Building Design Theory and Application

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ABSTRACT

Ecological thinking is the recognition of the dialectic unity between natural and man-made environment, the respect to everything that exists around us, and the concomitant “openness” toward others.

I assert that architects need adopt design and construction methods in conformity with the principles of ecology and be trained accordingly. No longer can good architecture claim to be good if it is not sustainably responsible. How can it achieve this target under the conditions prevailing today?

Environmental architecture and design, the theory and application of ecological thinking, are then directed towards the enrichment of the cultural environment, connecting the values of architecture with those of an ethical act under constant examination and redefinition. Environmental design requires awareness of the architect’s role, sensitivity and vigilance.

Although architecture puts forward the environmental design parameters, it responds at the same time to a large number of relevant issues: morphological, cultural and symbolic. In this way, it is not limited to energy saving, but rather oriented towards integration to the direct and wider environment, respecting the local scale, limiting the footprint and the optical nuisance of new construction. At the same time, the quest for inventive bioclimatic approaches also leads to experimentation with new materials and techniques that incorporate inter-local values. It thus becomes apparent that environmental architecture, appropriately taught, practiced and regulated is the way to protect the locus and its culture from the destructive forces of “uniformity”.

I will present examples in which I have been personally involved, to describe a number of passive bioclimatic approaches focused on the above principles, such as projects that explore the potential for using the wind as an expressive element in building design; projects that enhance cool air flow in the interior space, control wind and sand accumulation, protect from noise or enhance the sound carried by the wind, deflect prevailing winds, convert the wind into a means of protection against its own force, and others. Further to the wind treatment, I will present examples bearing adaptive building envelopes and shading systems to achieve control of natural lighting, ventilation and temperature of the inner spaces through their own transformability, surface openings and materials, including planting as a building material; in a sense, treating buildings as living organisms.

Three of these examples have been included in the H2020-MSCA-RISE OptArch project, in which I am scientifically responsible for the work package WP5 entitled “Improvement of bioclimatic design through optimization of performance”. The optimization results we have obtained will be separately presented in detail by other researchers in this Mini-symposium.

Motion Sequence Optimization of a Planar Structure

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ABSTRACT

Transformable rigid bar structures have variable geometrical and mechanical properties in order to adapt to changing external functional, environmental, or loading conditions. They usually succeed in shape transformations through integration and replacement of primary members and joints with mechanical actuators. Nevertheless, the systems often entail high energy amounts in their kinematics, affecting negatively their performance and adaptation behavior. In avoiding this and at the same time achieving flexibility, controllability, reduced structural self-weight and energy consumption, reconfigurations of planar rigid n-bar linkages have been proposed to build upon an ‘effective 4-bar’ mechanism. In principle, the ‘effective 4-bar’ approach, uses a sequence of one degree-of-freedom motion steps by selectively releasing four joints of the primary members at a time and engaging brakes installed on each individual joint and only one geared electrical motor at the base. Different intermediate configurations depend on the motion planning, in order to adjust the system's joints to the desired values during the motion steps involved from the initial to the target position. In the present study, we consider a principal planar 9-bar linkage with initial and target configurations defined on the basis of a quasi-ellipsoid shape of 5.42 and 4.49 m height respectively and 4.66 m span. The objective is to select the optimum motion sequence, in minimizing the brake torques in the locked joints of the structure. The investigation refers to the load-bearing behavior of the structure in all reconfiguration steps. The load cases considered in the analyses include the self-weight of the structure, a uniform distributed vertical load of 5 kN/m and a wind load of 2 kN/m. The numerical studies have been conducted with the software MATLAB and Simulink for a Model Based-Design. The geometrical, mass and inertia characteristics of the planar system, as well as the external load cases have been implemented in the algorithmic model. The work-minimization problem has been solved by means of the derivative-free Mesh Adaptive Direct Search (MADS) algorithm to avoid the possibility of inaccurate approximation of objective and constraint function gradients. The rigorous convergence properties of MADS ensure obtaining optimal solutions at reasonable computational cost, which facilitates the development of an agile structure with reduced-cost reconfiguration capability. The obtained results demonstrate that the design of reconfigurable structures can benefit from an automated optimization-driven analysis of their sequence selection, from the initial to the target position, for better performance and efficiency.

Design Optimization to Enhance Passive Energy Strategies. The KNOW HOWse Project for Solar Decathlon Middle East 2018

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ABSTRACT

The team coordinated by the University of Sharjah and comprising the Research Centre Architettura>Energia of the University of Ferrara – Italy, Shurooq – Sharjah Investment and Development Authority, and Sheikh Zayed Housing Programme, participated to the Solar Decathlon Middle East 2018 in Dubai (SDME) with the KNOW HOWse project. SDME, often referred to as the Olympics of sustainable architecture, is a competition where academic teams compete to design, build, and operate energy-efficient solar-powered houses. In the 2018 edition, 16 teams from around the world delivered a prototype house to the contest site in Dubai, and challenged each other in 10 contests evaluating different aspects of environmental design and energy management. The particular UAE climatic scenario implies consistent use of air conditioning throughout the year. For this reason, the KNOW HOWse project was developed to maximize the use of passive cooling strategies, in order to limit the electricity demand. This paper presents a summary of the long design process, aimed at optimizing the building shape to meet the SDME functional/size requirements, while at the same time enhancing the passive energy strategies, with particular regards to free-cooling ventilation techniques. More specifically, the design focused on the reinterpretation of traditional environmental strategies, such as cross-ventilation, *barjeel* (wind tower/catcher), and *qa'ah* (stack/chimney effect), merging them with innovative technologies and techniques. The use of energy simulation software significantly assisted the design development, optimized by iterations to achieve the ideal result. The optimized morphology of the house, finally built at contest site, indeed showed enhanced natural ventilation within the premises. Furthermore, the recoding of the energy consumed for active cooling, during the contest period, showed the positive reduction of air conditioning.

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Comportment of Wind Flow of Funnels Incorporated in the “House of the Winds” Designed by Agnes Couvelas

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents an experiment which interrogated the wind impact on architectural design. In particular, it intended to determine how architectural design can be enhanced over wind impact. The structural parts examined as case studies were the funnels incorporated in the “House of the Winds” in Santorini, Greece, designed by architect Agnes Couvelas.

The experimental method used was the wind flow simulation. The selected case studies were simulated in the environment of appropriate software, so as to examine their comportment over given wind flow situation. The software was ANSYS Discovery Live 19.0 which provides fluid flow solution by implementing the algorithms of fluid flow mechanics. After simulating the structures as constructed, every contour received multiple modifications related to its geometrical characteristics. Afterwards, every modification was set under simulation, pointing finally out the optimized shape.

In conclusion, it was proved the fluid flow simulation to be an instant procedure which presents the interrelation between wind flow impact and the building’s sustainability. It can be considered as a new tool towards the enhancement of architectural design. The familiar architectural process is so enriched with a manifold pre-construction control, achieving a sustainable and amiable design.

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Optimization of a Sail-Shaped Façade Structure of a Multi-Storey Office Building

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ABSTRACT

Human population on world is increasing drastically and uncontrolled way. This increase in population requires us re-think how we use resources. As a result of this, many researches come up in different disciplines about reducing the usage of resources to provide sustainable solutions of their discipline related problems. In architectural discipline, these studies not only aim to reduce material but also energy usage of the building since the building and construction related sectors are using 41.1% of the global produced energy. The share of energy consumption was 33.7% due to the population growth and people spend 90% of their lives indoor spaces which requires to be mechanically ventilated and air conditioned.

In this study, a multi-storey office building located in Athens is selected. The office building consists of four floors with west facing glazing façade that negatively affects the energy performance of the building and decrease the indoor quality by creating glare and overheating problems.

This study focuses on controlling daylight prevent glares and possible overheating of the office space by optimizing external hybrid shading devices geometries to increase the average useful daylight index while maximizing visual perception by genetic algorithm based heuristic approach.

Daylight model is created in Rhinoceros[®] modelling software Daylight calculations are done in radiance with the help of Ladybug and Honeybee plug-in of Grasshopper[®] parametric modelling plug-in of Rhinoceros[®]. For the optimization of the shading device geometry, OCTOPUS plug-in utilized for its ability to optimize multi-objective problems.

The result of the study shows that optimization of the external shading device affects the daylight performance and reduces the required energy for cooling the building during the summer period while satisfying the visual connection between indoor and outdoor. Not only a single solution for the problem but also some design alternatives are obtained due to the utilizing multi objective optimization method.

1st International Conference on Optimization Driven Architectural Design

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REGULAR ABSTRACT

Optimization in Vehicle Routing Problem

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ABSTRACT

The Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) is a general combinatorial optimization problem that has become a key component of transportation management. The VRP was first introduced by Dantzig & Ramser in 1959. General VRP is defined on a connected graph G . Let $G = (V, A)$ be a graph where V is a set of nodes (vertices) and A is the set of arcs (edges). Let $C = (c_{ij})$ be a cost matrix associated with A . The matrix C is said to be symmetric when $c_{ij} = c_{ji}$ and asymmetric otherwise. The vehicle must start and finish its tour at the depot and the problem is to construct at minimum travel cost. VRP lies between travelling salesman problem (TSP) and the bin packing problem (BPP). In combinatorial optimization, the TSP and the BPP are a NP-hard. The abbreviation NPhard refers to nondeterministic polynomial time hard. That means that it is not guaranteed that there is a known algorithm that solves all cases to optimality in a reasonable execution time. So in addition of an appropriate solution approach, a number of heuristics and meta-heuristics have been developed to find a solution to the problem.

In mathematics, computer science, or management science, optimization refers to the selection of a best element from some set of available alternatives. This symposium intends to invite front-line researchers to discuss all kinds of optimization technologies such as operations research, fuzzy logic, evolutionary computation, genetic algorithms and neural network, etc. Through this session, they are provided with a platform from there they exchange and share their experiences and research results about all aspects of Optimization especially in Vehicle Routing Problem. This session will also provide a forum for the interaction and integration in these related disciplines of Engineering Science.

Effect of Openings Ratio and Locations on The Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Shear Wall Systems

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ABSTRACT

Shear wall systems are one of the most common structural systems, which are used to resist lateral loads such as wind loads and seismic loads. These walls may contain openings for architectural requirements like doors and windows. Seismic design codes and guidance allow using different seismic analysis procedures for buildings having shear wall systems. However, these codes have not specified limit of the opening's ratios within such shear walls. This study aims to carry out a parametric investigation on the effect of square shear walls openings with different ratios from the wall area (i.e., 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%), and having different distribution with different locations (i.e., one-, two-, and staggered-openings). Response spectrum procedure is utilized for regular buildings to suggest the limit of openings ratio which can be used to satisfy requirements of seismic and architectural design. Number of stories investigated are six-, twelve-, and twenty-four stories with 3 m high for each individual story.

Based on the results of this study, it is observed that buildings tend to be more flexible, when the openings ratio increases. In addition, the study showed convergence in the response of buildings, when the ratios of openings are 0%, 10%, and 20%. Moreover, shear walls system losses much of its stiffness, when the openings ratio is 40% of shear wall area. When the ratio of openings is distributed to more than one opening, drift will be decreased compared to the case of having single opening. Finally, in order to have a reasonable structural performance, this study suggests to limit openings' ratio to 30% of total shear wall area.

Valorization of West Plastic Powder in Road Field

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ABSTRACT

In the framework of valorization of the worn tires and environment preservation, several techniques exist in many fields. In Algeria, and since 2005, about 19 facilities are carried out using the so-called 'Pneusol' technique. Currently, researches are interested in the use of rubber fine powder (RFP) that results from worn tires crushing. The letters constitute a cumbersome waste.[1,2]

The present work presents, beginning from an experimental investigation, the possible using of tire scrap in road coating. The main purpose of such mixture is to improve certain mechanical properties, and also to reduce waste materials in the urban or agricultural zones leading to environmental and human damage. The mean study approach refers to the behavior of asphaltic concrete containing fine powders. The latter is produced by crushing of rubbery products and worn-out tires through dry and wet processes. Changes in rheological laws and in mechanical properties of the bituminous powder mixture are checked by means of experiments.

The present study highlights the influence of fine powder content, size distribution and mixing conditions on some product properties such as deformation modulus, compactness and creep.

The experimental results of the whole survey lead to interesting correlations. In addition, the rubber fine powder (RFP) is recognized taking into account road and environment interests. This appears to be, economically, interesting.

Keywords: plastic fine powder - asphalt concrete - valorization - environment

Combining Mobile Robotics and Packing for Optimal deliveries

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ABSTRACT

The problem addressed is taken from warehousing and distribution. It concerns the order preparation in e-commerce. An order is a set of lines. Each line describes the ordered product (box) with its corresponding quantity. The problem consists of packing boxes subject to orientation, fragility, stackability, weight and volume constraints of various sizes into available containers (trays, cartons) in a way which optimizes the total number of containers to integrate in a number of delivery trips in e-commerce. The article addresses the problem where the packing is performed by a mobile robot. The aim of the work carried in the context of the project INCASE is to conduct a set of experiences where the packing activity is performed by a mobile robot based: (1) pick up items from shelves (2) and then pack items in boxes. To keep the problem simple, we assume that positions of items to pick up (1) and to place in the box (2) are known; they are computed by efficient bin packing optimization algorithms (2D, 3D) of Optim Suite of KLS OPTIM in production since many years. There are many ways of using bin packing algorithms. The first possible use is the online packing of items based on a fixed order defined by the host system. This approach has several drawbacks among them the inefficient handling of stability constraint and sub-use of available box volumes. The second approach is to allow packing algorithms to compute optimal or sub-optimal solutions whilst respecting all constraints. One the drawback of this approach is such solutions are not always feasible by a mobile robot. The idea is to relax such solutions in order to take into account mobile robots constraints. The objective is find a tradeoff between optimality and feasibility. The work is to conduct a set of real-life experiences and simulations by mobile robots to identify failures cases like falling, unsteady, damaged items due to robot arm forces, instability or space tightness (well optimized solution). The aim is to learn from these simulations, introduction of machine learning, and to derive a set of rules to integrate in the bin packing optimization algorithms as strategies to build robust packing solution for autonomous mobile robots.

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Towards Sustainable Building Design: The Impact of Architectural Design Features on Cooling Energy Consumption and Cost in Saudi Arabia

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ABSTRACT

Energy-saving has become a high priority in the Architectural design of buildings, particularly in hot climate regions like Saudi Arabia. Thus, selecting the appropriate Architectural Design Features (ADFs) at the early design stage provides significant opportunity to manage heat flow, prevent excessive energy consumption, and maintain a comfortable temperature for the occupants. In this research, a structured “Architectural Design Energy-Impact Scoring System (ADEISS)” has been developed. The system incorporates seven key ADFs that were identified based on inputs from a large number of experienced architects, and embody 40 different design options. To support designers in selecting and evaluating, including energy analysis, of any Architectural design that has any combination of design options, ADEISS incorporates a comprehensive decision scoring system. Energy analysis is performed using a simulation tool (Ecotect[®]) that is integrated with the Revit BIM models. To validate ADEISS, three design alternatives were evaluated for a residential building in Saudi Arabia. Thermal load analysis and cooling loads were applied to evaluate the impact of the selected design parameters on energy consumption and cost. Using ADEISS, it was possible to assess the design alternatives and arrive at the optimum design, which was supported by expert Architects. This research is expected to assist designers in understanding the energy cost implication of the key ADFs and presents a scientific decision-making approach to quantify the design alternatives while reducing designers’ subjectivity in the evaluation process. This research is also aligned with the growing calls for efficiency and sustainability in building design.

Sustainability Life-Cycle Evaluation of Timber Dwellings in North of Sweden Based on Environmental Impact and Optimization of Energy and Cost

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ABSTRACT

There is a need to balance environmental, energy and cost objectives during building design. Choosing high performance insulation materials, for example, might provide energy savings during the operational phase; however, they can significantly increase the embodied energy of the building to such a degree that the life-cycle energy consumption in fact is increased. Identifying design variations that strike the balance between these objectives can be aided with the use of multi-objective optimization. Given the presence of multiple objectives, the optimization gives rise to a set of optimal solutions. Without additional information, none of the Pareto-optimal solutions can be regarded as better than the others and selecting one solution from the set of optimal solutions remains a challenge. Thus, there is still research needed to increase the practical use of optimization for architectural, engineering and construction (AEC) practitioners [1]. This paper presents the use of a genetic algorithm [2] optimization approach where the results and environmental assessment are presented for and discussed with AEC practitioners. The method developed has been tested in two case studies: one prestige tourist cottage and one multi-residential building. The cottage was optimized based on an architectural drawing and the needs of the client. Different superstructures (timber frame and cross-laminated timber) and insulation materials and windows were varied for the building's envelope whilst evaluating life-cycle energy and cost. In addition, environmental impact in terms of CO₂ emissions was evaluated for initial and optimal design suggestions for the two different superstructures. The timber frame was found as the best solution. The multi-residential building was already in production for a real estate owner and the variables of this optimization were chosen to encompass a smaller design space: only the thickness of the insulation material was changed in the building's envelope as well as different windows. The results from this optimization show that the distribution of insulation could be adjusted where insulation from the roof and foundation could be made slightly thinner and the insulation in the exterior walls could be made thicker. The results from each case was presented and discussed with the stakeholders. For the first case, a report was written and then read by the stakeholder and used as base for future decisions. For the second case, the results were presented orally for the stakeholders. In both cases, it was possible to communicate the overarching results of the optimizations through visual plots using for example color-coding, although future research should find ways to also communicate the detailed results.

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Genetic Algorithm for Embodied Energy Optimization of Steel-Concrete Composite Beams

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ABSTRACT

The optimisation of structural performance is acknowledged as a means of obtaining sustainable structural designs. A minimisation of embodied energy of construction materials is a key component in the delivery of sustainable future designs. This study is the first component of a wider project to understand the relationship between embodied energy and structural form of composite floor plates for tall buildings, and how this form can be optimised to minimise embodied energy. As a search method based upon the principles of genetics and natural selection ^[1] Genetic Algorithms (GA) have previously been used to optimise composite beams ^[2,3,4] and composite frames ^[5] for cost and weight objective functions. Parametric design models ^[6,7] have also been presented as an optimisation tool to optimise steel floor plates for both cost and embodied carbon.

In this study, a Matlab algorithm is presented incorporating MathWorks global optimisation toolbox GA^[8] and utilising Eurocode 4 ^[9] design processes to optimise a composite beam for five separate objective functions: maximise span length; minimise beam cross section; minimise slab depth; minimise weight; and minimise deflected shape. For each of these objective functions, candidate designs are to be assessed for embodied energy ^[10] to determine individual relationships. It is anticipated that correlation can be derived, and collective relationships between design and state variables and embodied energy can be determined. To the authors best knowledge, such an approach has not been previously undertaken to determine relationships between design and state variables to embodied energy for a single beam. This initial study is

an important starting point prior to assessing more complex structures, and determining structural form as a function of embodied energy.

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Shape Optimization of Assembled Single-Layer Grid Structure With Semi-Rigid Joints

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ABSTRACT

It is generally known that the mechanical properties of connecting joints in assembled structures, such as strength and bending stiffness, have a great influence on the mechanical behaviour of the structure. Observations from earlier studies by Fathelbab (1987) confirmed that joint stiffness has a considerable effect on the load-displacement behaviour of a structure. Then, various types of joints have been experimented for their respective mechanical performances by Kato et al. (1998) and Ma et al. (2013), which have demonstrated different effects on reticulated shells. Furthermore, some new semi-rigid joints were developed by Feng et al. (2017), such as the ring-sleeve joint and the double-ring joint. It is worth to note that there are few studies of shape optimisation of assembled single-layer grid structure considering the effects of semi-rigid joints.

This paper takes the effect of the semi-rigid joints into account to optimise an assembled single-layer grid structure. Based on experimental results of the semi-rigid joints, finite element models of a single-layer grid structure with semi-rigid joints are established, and spring elements, as shown as Fig.1, are used to simulate the joint stiffness. The optimisation process is completed with the collaboration of ANSYS and MATLAB data. The research goal is to minimise the total strain energy. Genetic algorithm is used for the optimisation, and nodal z-coordinates are chosen as variables. The effect of the semi-rigid joints on the shape optimisation is studied by changing the joint stiffness. With this method, the optimal shapes of the assembled grid structure with different joint stiffness and improved buckling load are obtained.

Fig. 1 Space beam and virtual spring model

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Evaluation of Optimal Lateral Resisting Systems for Tall Buildings Subject to Horizontal Loads

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ABSTRACT

The tendency of modern designs towards optimal structures often leads to the lightest and best performing choice among a large set of design alternatives. In a similar scenario, the introduction of automated tools to further guide designers in achieving efficient solutions has been a recurrent topic for mechanical and structural engineers, over the past decades. Nowadays, topology optimization is considered a powerful preliminary design tool to determine the optimal material distribution in a design domain, i.e. the most effective configuration that satisfies a given set of prescribed constraints while reducing the consumption of structural material. Among different applications in the field of Civil Engineering, this work focuses on the definition of optimal layouts of lateral resisting systems for multi-storey steel building frameworks subject to lateral loads using topology optimization techniques. The objective of the research is to illustrate the benefits deriving from the introduction of automated routines within the preliminary design stage and establish reliable guidelines for performing accurate and objective optimization procedures. Since the optimal material distribution follows the load flow within the structure, optimal topologies are especially sensitive to the alteration of support and loading conditions: different loading scenarios naturally lead to distinct optimal layouts. In order to avoid the loss of objectivity and preserve the optimality of the results, the effects that preliminary modelling and loading assumptions produce on final layouts are investigated. Numerical applications to high-rise building models, with different aspect ratios and loading conditions, are presented and discussed. The problem is settled using a minimum compliance formulation to compare the material distribution results with those examined in the literature. Two-dimensional case studies are analysed via the topology optimization of a planar lateral resisting system, envisioned as part of a 3D building. The 2D representation, in fact, allows handling and dominating the basic issues generally arising in more realistic models, without adding further complexity to the problem.

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A New Model for Predicting the Transfer Length of Prestressing Strands Optimized Using Artificial Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

Effectiveness of prestressing is crucially linked to the transfer length (TL) of the stands. During the past decades, extensive experimental and theoretical research was conducted in this area, which led to the development of several models to predict the TL. However, majority of these models were developed based on either limited size of data points or accounting for certain key factors and ignoring others. The complexity in the TL determination is attributed to the requirement of a very powerful numerical technique that can digest the large size of data points and account for possible nonlinearities. For that, the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technique was used in this study for the prediction of the TL based on more than 458 data points collected from various literature works. The ANN technique allowed for investigating the effect of various key parameters classified into major categories including: strand characteristics, concrete properties, geometric details, and manufacturing method. The MATLAB software was utilized to build, train, and test the ANN using 19 input variables and one targeted output. The proposed ANN showed high prediction capability with low mean square error and the trend behavior of the TL versus certain key parameters showed good agreement with other published models. However, when all of the main factors that influence the TL are considered, the proposed model sensitivity analysis gave a good indication regarding the significance of the parameters influencing the TL determination. Moreover, an analytical model was developed using CurveExpert Professional software considering only the most significant parameters according to the ANN results and sensitivity analysis. The developed analytical model can accommodate effectively rectangular beam sections and AASHTO sections.

Multi-Axis 3D Printing of Material Reduced Shell Structures on Reconfigurable Supporting System Using Topology Optimization Principles

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ABSTRACT

The last few decades, the application of Additive Manufacturing (AM), and more specifically 3D Printing (3DP) techniques in construction scale, e.g. Contour Crafting (CC) [1], has shown an increase trend, with advantages in maximization of construction speed as well as minimization of material waste and construction cost. A number of constraints are also observed, mainly in relation to the printing of complex geometries due to the limitation of existing techniques, which are mostly applied in 2.5-dimensional shapes and with overhanging restrictions at specific angles. This work takes into account existing limitations at construction scale of 3DP of shell structures [2] and suggests a methodology for their parametric design and on-site fabrication using topology optimization principles for printing on a reconfigurable supporting system. Particularly, the process involves five steps: parametric design, topology optimization, functionally graded structural elements form-finding, formwork development and 3DP. In the first stage where parametric design is investigated, the catenary concept is used for the overall geometrical configuration of free-form shell structures aiming at minimization of exercised tension and compression forces. Then, topology optimization principles are applied in order to reduce total material volume and at the same time to achieve structural stability of the selected free-form shells. This is followed by a methodology for alternating individual unit members that follows the concept of functionally graded cellular structures [3], which aims at material distribution and customization in different areas. In the fourth stage, a reconfigurable formwork system is developed consisting of identical joints, flexible linear elements and membranes on top, in order to act as supporting structure allowing on-site 3DP in different angles and for different design configurations. Finally, the 3DP process of toolpath development and simulation are demonstrated, accompanied by real scale physical experiments with an industrial robot and a clay-based material extruder. The work is assessed based on the results obtained in the investigations, which might provide a positive impact on the construction of three-dimensional shell structures.

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StructurePlus: Structural Optimization Web-Application Platform with Parallel Processing and Cloud Computing

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the progress of practical structural engineering optimization software, has not gone much beyond aerospace engineering and mechanical engineering. This is obvious from comparison of the number of structural optimization software's in these domains too.

The most significant issue is the numerous volume of production in aerospace and mechanic engineering fields requiring unique designs, which justifies dedicating time to optimize them. However, in optimizing the design of a building, each single building has a unique design, and usually time is short for optimization.

As a result, the use of Artificial Intelligence and Metaheuristic Algorithms will generally be subject to a time constraint.

Although parallel processing in such cases can solve the problem, it is always facing limitations in software costumer's hardware.

In this study, for the first time, an innovative Web-based optimization software has been introduced with parallel processing and cloud computing capabilities. This software can provide computing hardware with no restriction for users globally.

Also it has the ability to use more than 10 metaheuristic algorithms and has been tested and verified for concrete and steel structures.

The Optimum Reinforced Concrete Deck Stiffness of Cable-Stayed Bridge Decks

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to find the optimum deck stiffness in terms of vertical deformation and cable stresses. The feasibility of this study was achieved by analyze and develop eighteen models using ABAQUS software with different deck stiffness's girder cross sections. Nonlinear static finite element analysis was performed on the simulated models. The stress results obtained from the static finite-element analysis of the cables without prestressing are employed in the prestress analysis. After that, pre-tensioning forces are applied to the cables. Subsequently, the shape modes for each model are introduced as well as the stress values before and after tensioning are executed. The results show that the maximum stress found at maximum deck stiffness and the maximum cable stress found at maximum girder cross section. Also, the deflection decreased dramatically with the increase of deck stiffness. Furthermore, the implementation of initial prestressing forces shows significant reduction in the maximum cable stress and maximum vertical displacement. Therefore, the relationship between the vertical displacement and deck stiffness is inverse. According to the data obtained and collected from these simulated models, the concrete deck slab with 50 MPa grade is the optimum grade in terms of strength and serviceability requirements.

Optimum Configuration of CFRP Composites for Strengthening of Reinforced Concrete Beams Considering the Contact Constraint

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the use of carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites for external strengthening of reinforced concrete beams is becoming very popular. This is due to the CFRP composites' high strength to weight ratio, durability, ability to form complex shapes, high elastic modulus, and high tensile and compressive strengths. Previous studies in this field showed that the increase in strength and stiffness by the CFRP composites is dependent on the direction of the reinforcing fiber (orientation), the CFRP sheet width, and number of layers of CFRP sheets. In this study, finite element analysis (FEA) was conducted using ABAQUS to simulate and evaluate the response of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with different configurations of CFRP composites. The investigated parameters include: the number of layers of CFRP sheets, compressive strength of concrete (30-70 MPa), and orientation of CFRP sheets. The beams were 1500 mm long with cross-section dimensions of 100 x 200 mm, loaded as simply supported beams under three-point loading configuration. Concrete damaged plasticity model was chosen and the models were calibrated and validated properly. The performance enhancements cannot be achieved without ensuring strong bond between the CFRP composite and the beam surface. Therefore, the nature of the contact between the CFRP composites and concrete was carefully evaluated in order to arrive at the optimum contact definition. The results showed that the performance of the beam was noticeably improved using up to three CFRP layers; any number of CFRP layers above three were ineffective. Therefore, it is important to optimize the number of sheets in a CFRP composite based on the beam dimensions and reinforcement to minimize the cost and avoid adversely affecting the ductility of the strengthened beam. Regarding the influence of concrete compressive strength, the enhancement in the performance of the CFRP strengthened beams was pronounced between 30 MPa and 40 MPa concretes; whereas a slight enhancement was shown when using strength higher than 40 MPa, in comparison with the 40 MPa concrete. The use of U-shaped layout of CFRP composites was the most effective configuration. Finally, the results indicated that the use of shell to solid coupling contact constraint shows the least percent error while allowing the relative movement between the beam surface and the CFRP composites.

Parametric Analyses for the Evaluation of Soil-Structure Interaction Effects on Eigenfrequencies and Damping Ratios

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ABSTRACT

The present paper evaluates the effects of soil-structure interaction on the eigenfrequency and damping ratio related to the translational degree of freedom of the superstructure of a 3DOF system. The degrees of freedom correspond to: i) translation of superstructure; ii) translation of foundation and iii) rotation of foundation. The discrete analytical model exploits frequency dependent impedance functions of a foundation supported at the surface of a nondissipative, homogeneous, linearly elastic halfspace.

The interacting system does not possess classical normal modes and a standard modal analysis is not rigorously applicable. Therefore, numerical free vibration experiments are performed applying a code written in MATLAB, in order to estimate modal characteristics.

Parametric analyses are conducted with changes in wave parameter, taking into account the variation of the following measures: i) Poisson's ratio of soil; ii) slenderness ratio of superstructure and iii) mass ratio of superstructure and foundation. Results indicate that soil-structure interaction effects decrease the eigenfrequency but may either reduce or increase the damping ratio. In the small value range of the wave parameter there is an increase of the damping ratio; in the medium value range a decrease may be detected while in the high value range, usually is equal to the structural damping. The decrease of Poisson's ratio leads to a more flexible system but with smaller damping ratio. Finally, the increase of foundation inertia increases the damping ratio, especially for small values of the wave parameter.

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Optimization of Tubular-Flat Trusses for Composite Floor Decking

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ABSTRACT

The use of composite floor truss in steel structure construction became more widely option that provides the designer great flexibility in space planning and in creating architecturally significant structural system. The significance of this study initiates from the need to produce a guidance on selecting of scheme, span range and span-to-depth ratio of the composite floor truss system for a particular application area providing optimum performance and cost effectiveness. With this objective a parametric study was designed, based on three parallel chord trusses (Pratt, Howe, and Warren), four composite floor European-profiles and ranged of loads intensity. Hence, the span-to-depth ratio (S/D) and dead-to-live loads ratio (DL/LL) were ranged from (3-27) and (0.84-3.22), respectively, for each truss type. The optimization was performed by using the design results of RFEM (2018) software for approximately 1000 models with the objective function of minimizing the cost function including the material, fabrication and painting costs. As a results, this paper also attempts to introduce a cost function in term of span-to-depth ratio and dead-live ratio for composite floor trusses.

Shaping the Microclimate. CFD-Assisted Design Optimization to Enhance the Outdoor Comfort of a Recreational Complex in the UAE

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ABSTRACT

The UAE Government has recently endorsed new regulations aimed at ensuring the sustainable development of the country. More specifically, the UAE Vision 2021 National Agenda focuses on improving the quality of air, preserving energy resources, and generally minimizing the electricity consumption in the built environment by implementing green-building practices.

As a matter of fact, the atrophic built environment is among the reasons for climate change, as a direct impact and modification to the original natural green-field. Buildings influence the surrounding microclimate, most of the time in an uncontrolled manner, eventually causing Urban Heat Island and Urban Air Canopy effect, and artificially modifying wind patterns.

This is furthermore true for the UAE, where the uncontrolled construction activity of the last decades has heavily modified the environment, already penalized by the extremely hot and humid climate that causes outdoor spaces to be scarcely used throughout the year.

This paper presents a design study assisted by Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) software simulation to optimize the design and shape of an outdoor recreational/retail complex in Sharjah, UAE, in order to achieve better environmental conditions and comfort and extend its usage period.

In fact, outdoor recreational/retail complexes in the UAE are only used in wintertime, approximately from November to March, when the weather is mild (about 40% of the year). Considering that these complexes make revenues for about half a year, it could be asserted that their construction cost is twice the cost of a building that is fully operational the whole year round (like a conventional closed mall).

The building shape has been modeled according to an iterative process assisted by CFD analysis: step by step the shape has been modified in order to increase the ventilation in the premises, with the aim of reducing temperature and humidity with particular regard to the mid-seasons of the year (end of fall and beginning of spring).

The preliminary outcomes of the study show that the optimized design could increase the typical usage of the outdoor complex to 58%, with substantial social, energy, and financial benefits.

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Adaptable Emergency Shelter: A Case Study in Generative Design and Additive Manufacturing in Mass Customization Era.

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ABSTRACT

The current paper aims to discuss the viability of digital fabrication and its optimization requirements in architectural design processes, through the analysis of an emergency sheltering solution scenario as it occurs within a generative design approach. The emergency case study is ideal to explain the necessity for optimal cost and time production, as well as topological optimization techniques through finite element analysis software, which allows for the production of optimal outcome concerning structural and aesthetic requirements. The aim of the project is not to provide a standardized design outcome, but is closer to create a heuristics solution platform, where processes of dynamic modeling could optimize several parameters of the shelter - if inputs such as specific geo-location are given - in order to perform efficiently in several differentiated environments.

In contemporary architectural design, digital technologies are increasingly being used not as a merely representational media for form-visualization but as a generative tool for the derivation of form and its transformation. Form-finding methods should be incorporated into the very first steps of the creative design process, rather than follow them as means of evaluation of an already designed outcome. It is crucial that architects should not consider this as means of form liberation only, but more importantly as an opportunity to a hands-on incorporation of i.e. structural, mechanical values and parameters into the design process itself. Representation plays an essential part on the design process and therefore should not be considered as an autonomous, individual task, preceding fabrication, but rather more of a holistic entity, where the means of representation play a key role in its capacity to include information about e.g. optimal structural and material properties and behavior. This is why representing architecture through computer systems simulation should not be regarded as a peripheral practice, but as a core procedure in design methodology, since design thinking, representation and construction are not distinct and sequential processes, but interconnected loops with continuous interactions.

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Design and Creation of an Energy Efficient Prefabricated Housing Unit based on Specific Taxonomy and Optimization Techniques

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to examine the integration of environmental systems and strategies in environmentally friendly and technologically advanced, off-grid prefabricated housing units. The study is based on a comprehensive precedent and literature review of current and proposed applications of prefabricated assemblies and their inherent potential, from the point of view of both design and construction, to accept the integration of the systems mentioned above.

A fundamental classification and taxonomy of the current state of the field was performed, aiming to create a tool for its adequate understanding. More specifically, the organization is based on three key design aspects in relation to the holistic approach of the issue of environmental design: Energy efficient structures, bioclimatic design and ecological approach to design.

All cases are addressed in terms of the challenges faced in optimizing the overall design performance so that it leads to an affordable and spatially flexible and site adaptable construction and in minimizing the units' lifecycle operational costs with an emphasis on energy consumption.

Based on the above taxonomy and optimization techniques, the research team is working on a new, off-grid prefabricated residential model, the "Prefab Eco Smart House", aiming to harmonically blend the prefabrication technology, bioclimatic design, integration of renewable energy sources, innovation in architectural design, comfort and technological excellence.

The ultimate aim of this effort is to critically present the breadth of typologies and the plethora of alternatives which can be applied on a green prefabricated building unit, in ways which optimize its design and energy potential.

Keywords: optimization-driven design; prefabricated housing units; renewable energy technologies; taxonomy; integrated technologies; passive design strategies.

The Impact of Installing a Concave Curved Profile Blind to A Glass Window on Visual Comfort in Office Buildings

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ABSTRACT

Daylighting design is regarded as one of the most promising strategies in improving energy efficiency by reducing fossil fuel consumption, while enabling the creation of a more pleasant work environment for occupants. In office buildings in particular, the use of natural lighting is highly favorable, as sufficient levels of visual comfort can be achieved, resulting to a drastically improved working environment with positive effects on employees' productivity and well-being. The task of bringing daylight into deep plan office buildings with conventional windows, or skylights, proves to be a challenging one and leads to the conclusion that the integration of innovative daylight systems in architectural design must be given serious consideration.

The question of this research arises from the challenge to investigate recent developments in daylighting design. The main objective is to explore advanced daylighting system profiles which enable the optimization of the visual comfort in office building interiors.

This paper describes the first stage of the research and focuses on the investigation of a daylighting system integrated on building envelopes, which explores the potentials of concave curved profiles in optimizing illumination levels of a deep plan indoor space, commonly found in office buildings. A ray-tracing analysis was developed to define the profile of the blind's reflective surface by estimating its lighting behavior. As results show, when the curvature of the substructure elements decreases, then the scatter diagrams obtained were still diffused with all the incident sunlight directed towards the inside of the room.

Daylighting simulations were generated, using Diva for Rhino v5.0 to evaluate the selected profile daylighting performance in three representative space typologies, taking an unshaded window as reference. The results are promising as the model system, in general, outperforms the reference case as it successfully increases an even distribution of light levels across the room and is thus, more likely to provide visual comfort.

Keywords: optimization-driven design; daylighting design; concave curved profiles; daylighting systems; visual comfort;

A Case Study on the Selection of Optimum Loop Units for the Deployable Arc Structures Exposed to Lateral and Non-Uniform Gravity Loads

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ABSTRACT

Radially deployable arches may be created by using various types of units. However, for any deployable structure to be constructed in real life, it should satisfy the structural regulations and codes. Despite various advantages from architectural perspective, deployable structures are weak to satisfy the operational code limits when compared to trusses with similar height and span. Therefore, weight minimization is very important to reduce the dead loads of structure which in return help to facilitate the code-conformance of structure. The optimization of deployable structures requires an initial selection of the loop unit types to define the structure parametrically. An initial selection strategy depending on the loads on the structure is important to increase efficiency of optimization process. Under uniform gravity loads optimum arrangement for each unit type converges to a similar point. However, in real world, the loads on the arches are not always uniform and the structure is exposed to non-uniform loadings such as point loads or lateral loads. This work focuses on the performance of various arches with different unit types under lateral and non-uniform vertical loads. Different lateral load and non-uniform gravity loading scenarios are created. For each scenario, arches with different units are analyzed. In all cases the clear span and clear height kept the same. Performance of an arch with a specific unit type for a given load is measured with a score that includes the deformations and the weight of the structure. All the members are assumed to be circular hollow sections with variable diameter and thickness to have a meaningful weight comparison between structures. This work intends to define an initial selection guide for deployable arches under typical non-uniform and lateral loading conditions.

Generation and Evaluation of Lightweight Door Frame Concepts

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ABSTRACT

Companies in the transport sector are always looking for ways to reduce the weight, with a minimal impact on cost and without negative effects on performance. Because of the ever more stringent regulations on emissions, weight reduction remains a top priority and is becoming a must. Moreover, decreasing weight leads directly to a decrease of fuel consumption, which, in turn, represents a strong competitive advantage. Weight optimisation of the current solutions (mainly based on traditional steel constructions) has reached its limit and can, in most cases, only lead to limited (5-10%) reduction in weight. To achieve substantial weight reduction, companies within the transport sector have to develop new and innovative concepts for their products in terms of geometrical design, material and joining technology.

The general objective of this research is to generate and evaluate new alternative concepts, by automatically exploring the design space, starting from a formal description. We demonstrate this methodology on a lightweight (interior) door frame. The outer door plate needs to be supported, the door must be able to open and close, and protect the interior from an impact.

The concept generation is split up in 2 different design steps; 1) generating an abstract door topology i.e. the number of beam elements and their connectivity and 2) generating feasible geometries for a given topology. By separating the two steps, we aim to generalize our approach, such that it can be applied to other design domains, like finding a chair with 3 legs and 1 armrest that will not tip over.

1) topology generation

2) geometry generation

Both generation steps are implemented as constraint programs, where we take as many functional and non-functional requirements as possible into account. The topological constraints can include a maximum number of beams that can come together in a joint, while geometrical constraints can deal specifically with the minimum angle between two beams required to allow easy welding.

The method results in feasible concepts, that can be further evaluated using more detailed attribute models for the objective evaluation of functional (weight, strength/stiffness, fatigue, and NVH) and non-functional (cost, manufacturability and robustness) attributes.

Assessment of Daylight Performance and Impact of Shading Devices for Typical In-Patient Rooms in Healthcare Facilities in Cyprus

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ABSTRACT

Natural lighting access is correlated with the heating and cooling loads of a building, therefore, with the overall energy consumption. This study aims to carry out a research on natural lighting performance and energy consumption of the most common room typology used for in-patient units in healthcare facilities. A preliminary literature review is carried out for the lighting assessment in healthcare facilities, emphasizing the correlated energy performance. Moreover, computer simulations were conducted using the IES-VE software; an advanced tool widely used among engineers. The research focuses on a typical double room (3.5m * 5.5m) with four orientations (North, South, East, and West). Different architectural designs are investigated, such as different glazing properties, shading devices, and light-shelves, in order to correlate daylight and energy performance to reach the best optimizations. For the natural lighting assessment, climate-based metrics were used including Spatial Daylight Autonomy (sDA) which correlates with artificial lighting need and the Annual Sunlight Exposure (ASE) which correlates with solar gains and glare. The study presents the differences in natural lighting quality, heating loads and energy consumption for each orientation and architectural configuration. Significant discrepancies are found between the above options which show that further systematic research is necessary in order have the optimum performance in both assessments.

KEYWORDS : Natural Lighting Analysis Simulations, Energy Performance, Artificial Lighting, Typical In-Patient Rooms, Healthcare Facilities, Daylighting Performance Metrics, Climate-based Daylight Modeling

Fixed Charge Minimum Cost Network Flow Approach to Optimize Product Assembly

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ABSTRACT

In manufacturing companies, assembly cost and lead time is often non-negligible. However, it is still challenging to estimate these values during product design. Moreover, not only product design affects this cost, also the furnishing of the assembly cell and the partitioning in subassemblies, which, for example, allows parallelization. This work focuses on this latter subject. Starting from a task description, the optimal assembly order is determined. An assembly order is in fact a permutation of all parts of the product that fulfills a number of constraints. These constraints consider the links between the parts, but also design for assembly restrictions. This information can be gathered in a directed graph in which each node represents a set of parts (i.e. subassemblies) and the edges define a lattice of subparts (i.e. an edge from node A to node B indicates that B is a subset of A). The capacity of an edge is determined by the cardinality of the set of the incident node. The cost of an edge is determined by the assembly complexity to split the larger assembly in the smaller subassembly. Each assembly order is a directed rooted tree in this graph, with the root node the node representing the set of all product parts and the leaf nodes the nodes representing a single product part. Furthermore, each non-leaf node in this tree is the parent node of two complementary sets, an example is visualized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of a split in two complementary subassemblies.

The optimal assembly order is the tree of lowest cost that satisfies the previous conditions. The problem differs in three ways from a standard minimum cost network flow problem [1]. First, there is a fixed charge for each edge that is used. Second, the edge costs are expensive to calculate, since simulation in a CAD program is necessary, so costs are only calculated on demand. Third, the final subgraph is a binary tree as described earlier. These differences require an adaptation of the existing algorithms for solving minimum cost network flow problems. The paper shows an efficient approach to tackle these challenges. This results in an assembly order that is feasible, fast and of as little complexity as possible. The resulting assembly order is compared to assembly orders obtained by bottom-to-top and other current rule-based approaches [2] on a number of performance indicators, e.g. feasibility, complexity and parallelization.

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Parametric Investigation for the Improvement of the Overall Sustainable Performance of an Innovative Masonry Wall System

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the additional optimization of the overall sustainable performance of an innovative masonry wall system that consists of modular construction components. These components consist of a novel mix design, whereby 50% of the binder by weight is replaced by waste mineral additives, while sand is partially replaced by limestone filler, thus decreasing the overall environmental burden.

The masonry units consist of a load-bearing block, featuring an embedded extruded polystyrene insulation sheet and an external coating layer. Although the masonry system exhibits sufficient thermal performance with low environmental impact, compared to other typical masonry systems, a further improvement can be achieved by a parametric study of its geometry.

The present study investigates alternative geometric configurations of the masonry system and alternative void patterns of the load-bearing block, in order to further improve its overall performance. The investigation aims to find the optimal solution in terms of thermal performance, environmental impact and structural integrity.

Heat flux numerical simulations are carried out using FE models, both for steady-state and transient heat analyses, to assess the thermal performance of the aforementioned system in terms of U-value, time lag and decrement factor, while data from the literature are used to compute the wall's environmental impact in terms of embodied energy. Furthermore, Finite Element (FE) simulation is conducted to assess load resistance.

Based on the findings, a significant improvement of the thermal performance, and a reduction of the embodied energy of the masonry system, can be achieved with proper geometry configurations and void pattern without affecting its structural integrity.

Geometric Assembly Cell Design Space Exploration

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ABSTRACT

The design of the geometric layout of a properly setup production cell is not an easy task. Different goal values are often important: cost, lead time, cell area, ergonomics, Furthermore, different constraints apply, as the design of the geometric layout has to be physically feasible and safe. These constraints include non-overlap of the different physical elements in the cell as well as box -and reach constraints. The different goal values and constraints characteristic of the problem result in a very large, non-linear search space. This makes solving these types of design problems very challenging, potentially leading to very large computation times. In order to develop a useable design tool, that explores the design space in order to support a cell designer, the underlying optimization problem should be solved efficiently. This is particularly relevant if the tool includes user feedback and other types of interactions with the designer. This paper handles an efficient solution of the cell layout design space exploration, using a gradient based optimization approach to solve the problem. We describe models for different goal and constraint functions, i.e. for computing the ergonomic score, lead time, safety and many of the physical constraints related to the cell design and how these are used to solve the complex optimization problem. In order to efficiently solve the problem, especially for more involved cell layouts, simplified models are put forward that approximate the goal functions and constraint functions in order to reach a gradient that is smooth enough. This is particularly necessary for very non-linear constraints, like, for example, non-overlap constraints for collision detection. This method allows to supports the designer in comparing different cell layout designs, for example using Pareto front analysis of different designs. Our approach is applied to an example cell design, where robots and a cobot interact with multiple human operators during the manufacturing process.

Example of the geometric layout of a work cell.

Optimization of Test Case Allocation Scheme in Program Partition Testing

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ABSTRACT

A comparison analysis of some various test case allocation schemes in software partition testing is presented in the paper. The set of all relevant inputs to a program is usually referred to as the program's input domain. Exhaustive testing which tests all possible inputs is generally impractical since the inputs domain is normally very large. Typically, testers can only afford to test a small part of the input domain. Random testing and partition testing are commonly followed practice towards selection of test cases. For partition testing, the program's input domain is divided into subsets, called partitions, and one or more representatives from each partition are selected to test the program. In random testing test cases are selected from the entire program's input domain randomly. Random testing can be viewed as a degenerate form of partition testing in the sense that there is only one partition, ie. the entire program domain. The process of dividing the entire program's input domain into partitions is generally very labor-intensive and expensive. Therefore, it would be expected that testing with partitions will be more effective than random testing, which does not require such a division. It turns out however [1-2] that even when partition testing is better than random testing at finding bugs, the difference in effectiveness is marginal. Therefore, since partition testing is more expensive than random testing, it is interesting to know the conditions when partition testing will always be more effective than random testing in terms of cost per fault found. Weyuker and Jeng [1] found that if all partitions are disjoint and of equal sizes, then by selecting equal number of test cases from each partition, partition testing is at least equally effective as random testing in detecting at least one failure. This condition has been generalized by Chen and Yu [2]. They proved that if the partitions are disjoint, then partition testing is better than random testing so long as test cases are selected in proportion to the size of partitions.

This paper contains a description of the use of some results of the works [1-2] in the process of testing a program with a known modular structure. The paper examines the problem of determining the program testing scheme with a known modular structure. As a measure of reliability of the program under testing the probability of its correct execution for a randomly chosen test case is assumed. The impact of the used testing scheme in partition testing method on the value of this measure is analyzed. The main result of the paper is the proposal to implement the program testing process based on the testing scheme being the solution to the optimization task, maximizing the value of the assumed reliability measure of the tested program. The presented considerations are illustrated by a numerical example.

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Optimization of Bus Stops Locations Using GIS Techniques and Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

Optimization of public transportation network in terms of reducing travel time and providing sufficient access to the service facility would certainly motivate private car owners to use public transport. The reduction of vehicle numbers on the roads will undoubtedly lead to minimizing traffic congestion and reducing air pollution due to lesser exhaust emissions. This study used Geographic Information System (GIS), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) to model the location of bus stops in Amman city in Jordan to find optimal travel time and serviceability of stops. The GIS modeling provided significant reduction of travel time for streets with redundant bus stops located at irregular distances, e.g. Zahran Street, where travel time was reduced by (23.25%) during off-peak hours and by 19.74% during peak hours, while PSO provided (28.95%) and 39% reductions, respectively. GA also provided significant reduction in travel time (47.96 %) for Zahran Street.

For streets with insufficient number of bus stops, travel time went up due to increase in the number of stops, e.g. Al-Quds Street, where travel time increased from 12.25 min per route to 50.71 min due to increase in the number of stops from 6 to 25. In contrast, this increase in travel time significantly reduced the walking distance to the bus stop, from over 2000 m to approximately 400 m. Moreover, demand for bus stops serviceability significantly more than capacity. Average demand per bus stop on Al-Quds street, for example, was 10456 persons with a capacity of 1465. Comparison of the models by applying them to roads not included in the study showed consistent results that further confirmed the reliability of the models. The developed PSO algorithm and GA are easy to use for urban planning, where they can be applied to any existing network or planned development.

Dynamic Response of RC Bridge Span Subjected to Blast Wave Shock

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this paper is to investigate the blast response of bridge span located at the vicinity of high explosive (HE) charge. These explosive tests will assist understanding the dynamic behavior and develop confidence in the computer model. A robust 3D computational model will be created using ANSYS and blast analysis will be simulated using LS-DYNA software. The model will be refined and calibrated using design of experiments (DOE) techniques to record responses that are good agreement with the experimental responses. Extensive full factorial experiments on the model will be carried out to determine simultaneously the individual and interactive effects of many factors that could affect the dynamic response of the simulation.

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Thinking Outside the Box: Small Diameter Sheaves Replacing Big Sheave for Vertical Lift Bridge

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ABSTRACT

AASHTO Standard specifications for Movable Highway Bridges has provisions for the use of small diameter sheaves. The provisions are seldom used and may not be understood by most. This paper will discuss the requirements of the AASHTO Movable Bridge Specifications and how small diameter Sheaves can be used in movable bridge applications. This paper will also discuss rope fatigue in general in order to provide some back up as to how and why these provisions were established.

This paper will show use the AASHTO provisions for small diameter sheaves to prepare alternate designs, and the cost of various alternatives will be compared. A preliminary design for Illinois Street Intermodal Bridge will be presented as an example.

Optimization of Daylighting and Energy Performance in Hot - Arid Climate

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ABSTRACT

The daylighting performance, besides the thermal comfort of the buildings is extraordinarily needed to be determined at the early phases of design. In addition, the building envelope is playing a vital mediator between the building and the surrounding conditions whether perceptible as climate change or intangible like cultural heritage identity.

So that, studying responsive architecture for sustainable buildings by developing the daylighting performance, and reducing the energy consumption of the buildings are important scopes for getting rid of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, in order to adapt and mitigate climate change and occupants' satisfaction.

Currently, the hot-desert countries are carrying out the design strategies based on the fully glazed buildings as in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), called 'the International Style', which was established for another climate. This causes an inefficient building performance coupled with identity crises.

Furthermore, any strategy aims at decreasing exaggerated solar radiations and improving availability of daylight is deemed a sustainable strategy for design. There are also limited performance evaluation tools offered to architects at the early phases of design.

In this context, this paper is going to present the assessment principals for energy performance in the case-study. This sets the principles for optimizing daylighting performance in hot and arid climates like in the UAE by making the best use of performance simulation analysis and parametric generic algorithm software, that is utilizing predetermined standards, at the several times all over the year. The adaptive building envelope is merged: (1) Shading devices; (2) Redirecting of the daylighting. It explores the benefits from two systems by integrating interactive louver device. It offers a new building performance optimization method, which can enable architects to estimate both energy and daylighting performance through making balanced design options and recognizes the relationship between design requirements and performance measurements. Therefore, this research aims to set the processes of performance optimization by utilizing simulation tools and technologies simultaneously with parametric design, and genetic algorithms. This will allow architects to scout the optimization for energy performance, and daylighting in hot - arid climate of several alternatives during the early design stages that is estimated to improve entire environments.

Optimum Endurance Time of Reinforced Concrete One Way Slab Subjected to Fire

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ABSTRACT

In concrete structures, determining the fire endurance time is fundamental so as ensure that structural elements be able to withstand an aggressive fire for a reasonable time period. Slabs are the most susceptible to fire damage because of their large surface area and shallow depth. Analyzing their bearing capability after sustaining fire requires the knowledge of temperature distribution in the cross sections, as well as thermal properties of concrete and embedded steel. In this paper, fire endurance a typical reinforced concrete one way slab is investigated analytically by using ANSYS in terms of time to failure and physical changes associated with exposure to failure. A nonlinear finite element (NLFEA) model was developed and validated by the experimental data before predictions were extended to investigate the significance of concrete density, concrete mechanical properties, and bottom concrete layer cover on the fire endurance time.

Optimization of Deployment Architecture in SOA systems

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ABSTRACT

Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) is still a popular way of building and integrating systems and it constantly evolves. In addition to the classic interpretation of SOA in which the Enterprise Service Bus (ESB) is used, there have also emerged new concepts of dividing systems into smaller and smaller components such as microservices. It turns out that in order to complete a business process or a complex service, it is necessary for many integrated components to work together. This integration in the SOA concept most often takes place through the network using the so-called Web Services. This leads to the emergence of an increasingly complex deployment architecture where the number of network connections, servers and virtual machines grows. Therefore, it is increasingly difficult to ensure optimal efficiency of the system. We define the effectiveness of a system as meeting four criteria. The first two criteria are the average duration of business processes in the system and the variance of this time (we strive to minimize these values). The other two are the amount of memory and processor resources reserved for these processes (which are also minimized).

The paper presents the method of optimization of Deployment Architecture in terms of these criteria. The term Deployment Architecture is understood in this paper as allocation of software components to servers and choosing such service selection and service scheduling algorithms that are the best match to the allocation. Service selection is the process of selecting an instance of a component. It is necessary because the component can be run on multiple servers at the same time. Service scheduling is an algorithm for selecting the order of service realization in case the component performs queued services (FIFO is not always the optimal choice).

The presented method of optimization of Deployment Architecture is based on the cooperation of a genetic algorithm and a SOA system simulator. The gene in the algorithm is a binary matrix for the allocation of components to servers. The genetic algorithm is run separately for each pair of service selection and service scheduling algorithms. The product of the method is a set of pareto optimal results from the perspective of the four criteria mentioned above. The most difficult element of the method is the evaluation of solutions. For this purpose, a mathematical model of SOA systems has been prepared. On its basis a simulator with three layers has been implemented. In the first layer, the infrastructure is simulated, and its most important elements are: server resources, the probability of server damage and bandwidth of network connections. The component (second) layer includes: load generated by runtime environments and components. The third layer focuses on business processes and the Web Services they invoke, as well as the use of intermediaries such as ESB. The results of the method will be presented towards the end of the paper.

Optimization Methodology of Improving the Design Of Shading Systems with Integrated PV for Office Buildings in Greece

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ABSTRACT

Fixed shading devices can improve the passive design of the building due to the fact that they reduce the energy needs for cooling in the summer. At the same time though they minimize the daylight availability in the interior space meaning that they increase the electricity needs for lighting and they increase thermal loads for heating in the winter according to their orientation and geometry.

In this paper we assess different geometries of fixed shading devices when used for south, east and west orientation using different simulation tools for the climate of Greece. At the same time due to the integration of PV in these geometries we assess the energy production that can be achieved in order to optimize their performance and minimize the total energy needs of the building.

Furthermore, in order to assess the developed methodology, we evaluate the design of fixed shading systems proposed for an office building in Greece according to their optimization performance. We reevaluate their contribution in the overall energy needs of the building when using PV integration into them and the possible influence of the integration into the final design improvement, the interior comfort conditions and the energy savings in relation to shading systems without integrated PV.

Efficiency Investigation and Optimization of Contract Management Business Processes in a Workwear Rental and Laundry Service Company

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents business processes business process models in the area of contract management in a workwear rental and laundry service company. The presented diagrams are the result of the analytical work performed by the multidisciplinary team of experts. The team consists of IT specialist, subject-matter experts and employees of the rental company. Models presented in the article consider the fact that parties to the contract request for changes in a completely electronic way. Submission of applications and performing business processes is carried out using the automated BPMS (Business Process Management System). Business models presented in the article are described in accordance with the assumptions of BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation).

The models the rental company's activities were created in the ARIS software environment, where the simulation of all necessary operations was carried out. As the result of simulation experiments a number of interesting parameters were obtained. There is no possibility to obtain these parameters in the static analysis of a business process. They can be only determined by the dynamic analysis. A sample results show the frequency of various significant events, accumulated time corresponding to activities performance, number of actions being performed by different people, overall working time for employees, the degree of the human factor use, and the global cost connected with different activities.

The following processes models have been developed, simulated and optimized: Release of an employee, Locker room change request, Clothing size change request for an employee, Cabinet location change request, Clothing sets amount change request, Personal data change, Employment process, Registration of the own clothing for an employee, New cabinet order, New set of keys set up, Transfer of an employee, Clothing repair request.

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Modeling and Characteristics Investigation of Warehouse Business Processes in a Clothes Clean&Rental Company

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents results of studies on modeling and characteristics investigation of business processes in a clothes clean&rental company warehouse. Business processes are mainly related to the activity of warehouse employees. Formal business process models are discussed and presented in the form of business process diagrams. Warehouse processes are aimed at streamlining and systematizing the activities carried out as part of warehouse management of workwear in Zwoleń (Poland). Warehouse processes have been optimized and designed in accordance with standard procedures performed in the warehouse. The following models of business processes were developed:

1. Demand for clothing - activities within the process are carried out by the warehouse employee at the moment when the demand for clothing appears in the system. The emergence of clothing demand is a consequence of other business processes or decisions made at quality control desk.
2. Acceptance to the warehouse - activities within the process are carried out by the warehouseman when there is a need to accept goods for storage. The result of activities is the full acceptance of clothing for the magazine.
3. Order to the warehouse - activities within the process are carried out, in the event of a justified need to order the additional items of clothing.
4. Warehouse inventory - activities within the process are carried out when there is a need to conduct an inventory of the whole warehouse or element of the warehouse.

Supply flow streams have been defined for warehouse work. Times and costs of task implementation were assigned to individual activities in business process diagrams. The times of actions are of stochastic nature. Event attributes in diagrams were also defined. Control flows in the diagrams are determined in accordance with the previously tested probability distributions.

In the ARIS environment, to simulate modeling, simulation and analysis of business processes, a simulator of the functioning of the warehouse was built based on and constructed business process diagrams. Dynamic characteristics (in relation to personal resources, times and costs) of the functioning of the warehouse based on numerous simulation experiments were presented.

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An Optimal Design Methodology for Planar Scissor Linkages Using Artificial Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

The required topologies for scissor linkage-based planar deployable structures have recently been classified by Kiper [1]. Such deployable structures have many applications in architecture. Determination the link lengths for planar scissor linkages is a difficult problem due to large number of links. Therefore linear search based optimization techniques result in high computational cost for such deployable structures. This study proposes use of Artificial Neural Networks to design the dimensions for planar deployable structures comprising scissor-like elements as assemblies of fundamental loops to obtain a given desired transformation of planar curves. The essential problem of this study is how to obtain the kinematic dimensions of these loops using artificial intelligence methods of optimization. The first step is to examine the desired motion of the structure. The given initial and final forms of a transforming curve are discretized to line segments. However, this discretization causes an error between the curves and the polylines. Thus, one of the critical aim of this study is minimize this error using proper optimization methods in the literature. The preferred fundamental loops and their assemblies are produced using line symmetry groups. The following loops are preferred because of their dominancy in applications: rhombus, kite, dart, parallelogram, anti-parallelogram. Link lengths are determined using artificial neural networks in order to minimize the error between the discrete and continuous curve forms. Different type of network structures and neuron types are evaluated to see the performance of the method. The methodology is illustrated with several examples for different types of deployable and transformable structures.

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Parallel Computing and Multi Thread Processing In Synthetic Data Preparation and Generation for Some Financial Crime Scenarios

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ABSTRACT

We present our two-tier parallelization method applied to fraud detection, where certain techniques of machine learning were used [1-3]. The first level of parallelization is based on multi thread 'static' data generation, which is limited to single (not yet related) 'objects' like persons and business entities. Subsequently, once the generated object population reached the required size, we dynamically create relationships between them. Thought in terms of network elements, these are nodes and vertices, respectively. During this part of our simulation was parameter-driven: we applied available probability distributions for the parameters to create certain situations which may be identified as 'crime'. The scenarios were either tailored to mimic predefined crime patterns and to be subsequently identified as such during testing our algorithms or were generating as 'suspicious'. In the latter case, depending on the sensitivity of our algorithms, we were able to evaluate how efficiently were our parallelized algorithms, running on multiple CPU units (cores), in identification of those subtle cases among millions of 'typical' scenarios.

The scope of our analyses were determined by the state legal regulations and business rules enforced by the public institutions which are to utilize our methodology. For this reason, rather than being granted access to real life data, the above restrictions were behind motivation to devise relevant and efficient solution where simulated data would closely mimic the real scenarios, including persons, businesses, transactions, relationships, locations etc.

The whole simulation processes comprised of generating artificial data which in real life were generated, operated and maintained by the following governmental systems: Universal Electronic System for Registration of the Population (PESEL) and the related information regarding persons' family and given names, addresses, birth certificates; The public register (KRS), maintained by selected district courts and the Ministry of Justice; Land Registers (KW) presenting the legal status of real estate; Central Register of Vehicles and Drivers (CEPiK); The General Inspector of Financial Information (GIIF); Social Insurance Institution (ZUS); Telecommunications billing (Billings); Customs Service (Celne); Register of the National Economy (REGON); Tax Identification Number (NIP).

The essential details of our approach is included in our paper.

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Methods and Analytical Tools for Assessing Tactical Situation in Military Operations Using Potential Approach and Sensor Data Fusion

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents designed quantitative methods and algorithms implemented in specialized mobile mCOP [1] application for combat decision support. Military operations require sophisticated planning and execution in order to minimize risks and potential losses while fulfilling mission objectives in constrained time. To support such features the decision makers design methods of evaluating threats and tactical scenarios. The outcomes of such calculations provide mission alternatives called variants or Courses of Actions. To determine which possible CoA is matching the scenario and in the end is the most feasible, a set of quantitative methods can be used. The evaluation process considers both tactical and topographical characteristics of the scenario. The location, orientation and composition of forces, combat potentials, performed tasks, as well as terrain and battlespace environment features are the parameters considered in the algorithms, which in result provide threat levels, attrition rates, potential losses, objectives timelines etc. To assess tactical situation we implemented, a set of combat potential evaluation methods, which using doctrinal patterns, can be easily employed in mobile software. The advantage of equipping each decision maker at the tactical level with sophisticated methods provides means of increasing the speed of task execution, provides more accurate decisions but most of all supports instant reporting from combat units. Due to the development of hardware and software platforms, smartphones offer are capable of running complex algorithms for tactical support for individual soldiers and low level commanders support. Since they are capable to utilize tactical data (forces location, composition, tasks) in dynamic mobile military networks, accessible anywhere during mission, and provide provides rich functional support for situation awareness and decision superiority. These two key factors of 21st century military operations influence the efficiency of recognition, identification and targeting during combat missions. Military support tools providing rich tactical and their analytical capabilities, can serve as recon data hubs, but most of all can support and simplify complex analytical tasks for commanders. The tasks mainly include topographical and tactical orientation within the battlespace. Developed software platform mCOP, demonstrates all research findings, providing personalized combat-oriented distributed mobile system, supporting blue force tracking capabilities, reconnaissance data fusion as well as threat level evaluation for functionalities for management of military and crisis management scenarios. Presented research demonstrates and evaluates the proves the usefulness of deploying mobile applications for combat support, situation awareness development, and the delivery of augmented reality based threat level analytical data to extend the capabilities and properties of constructed methods and of software tools applied for supporting military and border protection operations [2].

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Method for Designing Optimal Usable Structures of Computer System for its Emergency Reconfiguration

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ABSTRACT

The work deals with the reconfiguration of computer system, which was designed to provide services from a strictly defined set. We assume that the system is fully usable, as long as each randomly appearing request to perform any service from this set will be handled. When such a request occurs, the technical resources required for its fulfillment must be allocated to the service. In the general case, the same technical resources can be dedicated to perform various services at different moments of time. Therefore, it is advisable to introduce abstract resources, so-called functional ones, representing particular types of actual technical resources. Functional resources mediate in linking the services and technical resources required to perform them. One functional resource can be associated with only one service, whereas it can be performed by various technical resources.

Each set of pairs $\langle \text{service}, \text{functional resource} \rangle$, constituting a subset of the full set of such pairs, determined at the design stage of the system, creates the so-called the system's functional structure. In the case of damage of technical resource, it cannot be ruled out that it is impossible to maintain full usability of the system, i.e. to create an complete usable structure. However, as a rule, it will be possible to create more than one of its substructures, each of them provides support for service requests from a subset of the established set of services. If it is permissible to provide services to a limited extent for established subsets of services and for each of them a loss function resulting from the inability to provide a given service was specified, the system should be reconfigured (using available technical resources) so as to create a usable structure, at which potential losses will be the smallest..

The results of previous works are as follows:

- an algorithm for interactive fixing acceptable substructures by a user, reducing to the necessary minimum the number of required indications of service subsets (n services is 2^n possible subsets). Indeed, the choice comes down to establish vectors of minimal reliability functions. That algorithm has been implemented,
- a general algorithm for determining optimal functional substructures at a given state of fitness of the system. It can be the basis for the design of the layer for controlling automated system reconfiguration.

The presented approach allows to reduce losses in the case of a lack of full possibilities of supplying services by the system. The proposed method, after some extensions, can be applied to reconfigure non-computer systems, e.g. the state security system.

Quantum Optimization Methods for Frequency Selecting in Cellular Network Planning

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ABSTRACT

Soon, mobile operators will face the problem of building 5G network. This is a great challenge due to the optimization of costs of the new infrastructure while maintaining appropriate network parameters to ensure fast data transfer and the broadest coverage of the area.

One of the issues, that occurs during the design of cellular network, is planning the locations of base transceiver stations. Usually each station is equipped with directional antennas which cover some surface with a network signal. Every antenna transmits a signal of a given frequency. The high frequencies provide fast data transfer but this kind of the signal is also prone to damping (e.g. by leaves of the trees). In addition, the antennas, covering adjacent areas, must operate at different frequencies to avoid the interference phenomenon.

In our work, we would like to present a solution to the problem of appropriate frequencies selection with the use of quantum computing. The mentioned issue may be treated as the map coloring problem where the different colors refer to the different frequencies of transmitted signals [1]. The whole area, divided by the zones with different signal frequency, may be presented by the chimera graph [2]. Next, the problem may be brought to the Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) task [3]. Finally, we can utilize adiabatic computations implemented on the D-Wave quantum machine to solve the defined problem.

The paper is intended to contain the detailed description of the mathematical model necessary to express the problem of appropriate frequencies selection in the cellular network. We will construct some tasks which will be solved by the D-Wave quantum hardware: D-Wave Leap which is the quantum application environment accessible by the cloud service.

* The asterisk denotes the presenting author.

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Determining Working Piston Position for Hydraulic Pressure Amplifier Using Gradient Descent Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Efficient energy use is an overarching goal in modern industry. Energy managing, recovering and saving systems attempt to resolve this issue. One of these are hydraulic systems which are mostly used for industry and mobile applications. Wherever the high forces are required, like machine and power industry, transport or emergency appliances, the hydraulic systems are utilized. One of hydraulic system components facing energy management and power consumption issues is a hydraulic pressure amplifier (Fig. 1). This device generates high oil pressure what results in obtaining high force when it is required. In order to ensure simplicity and failure-free operating this kind of hydraulic valve bases on internal, hydraulic control. For purpose of amplifier modeling it is necessary to determine the position of working piston during its operation. This issue will be considered in the article.

Fig. 1. The hydraulic pressure amplifier construction

This paper covers general description of high pressure (HP) hydrostatic drive systems, hydraulic pressure amplifier principles of work and introduces a method to determine the position of working piston in such devices. The first part summarizes the capabilities and depicts the ways of obtaining HP by utilization of hydraulic pumps, hydraulic pressure intensifier and other energy storing hydraulic high pressure systems. The principles of hydraulic pressure amplifier work will be represented on functional diagram as well as described with crucial construction information. The significant part of this article is the determination of working piston position. Based on previous examinations results [1] (pressure changes in HP chamber) the position changing algorithm was implemented utilizing gradient descents optimization method. It was observed that the local minima and maxima of working pressure in time corresponds to working piston steering points. The results of calculations will be used in further works on hydraulic pressure amplifier model.

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The Framework for Assessing Similarity Measures Impact on Classification Confidence based on Probabilistic Record Linkage Model

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ABSTRACT

The notion of confidence has been recognized as an important outcome of a classification task. The presence of a measure that indicates how relevant the prediction is, improves a decision-making process by allaying uncertainty that ensues the bare labeled result. The number of different classification models available nowadays is extensive, and means to determine the confidence level must be adopted to pertain to specifics of the model [1].

The Fellegi and Sunter's Probabilistic Record Linkage Model [2] (F-S or PRL hereafter) is applicable to classification problems, where new observations are to be associated with the elements of a referential set. For each pair of a new observation and the referential set member, F-S determines its location in the result space. The result space comprises of regions labeling outcomes either links or unlinks, both separated by an area of uncertainty called clerical / manual review range. The space is founded on sameness of elements compared, defined as agreement pattern or comparison / similarity vector, and probabilities of their observation conditioning the pair is true match and un-match. Model merits a note, it's all parameters can be estimated based on unlabeled data [2, 3], accounting to PRL advantage as pertinent to unsupervised classification task, when actual linkage status is unknown.

Clerical review range is considered model classification confidence in the paper herein. The smaller it is, the more likely a pair of elements evaluated will be found either link or unlink, not in the ambiguous in-between state. As manual review region boundaries are determined with the use of probability density functions, grounded in agreement patterns relying on exploited similarity measures, the selection of the latter obviously has impact on the model classification confidence.

To rank different similarity models in this term, we built a framework to assess the effect a choice has on the clerical review range. The empirical results we have obtained with data coming from different application areas, proves how significantly similarity measure selection can determine the uncertainty PRL area. It implies framework plausibly useful for contributing to model classification confidence in different domains F-S can be used in, like medical diagnosis, fraud detection systems, person re-identification and other fuzzy or pattern-based labeling systems.

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Information Environment Model for the Analysis of Disinformation and Misinformation Spreading

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ABSTRACT

In 2016 in Warsaw during NATO summit cyberspace has been recognized as a fully-fledged military operation environment. National defence forces intensify work on possibilities to conduct operations, both technical or information, in cyberspace. Latter one, called INFO OPS, are aimed at society – its main goal is to affect behaviour and attitude to make them consistent with the attacker’s expectation, obtain an informational advantage, including communication control.

As the amount of information grows it is becoming more and more important to be able to model and simulate actions used in such operations. The article proposes a proof-of-concept model of informational environment for analysis of spreading of disinformation and misinformation which is one of key concepts of informational warfare. In order to understand the fake news spreading it is very important to take into account the behavior of a single agent in the network. Actions made on microscopic level affect the spread of the untrue information on the macroscopic level.

The proposed model can be used to analyze spreading of fake news on any social media like Twitter or Facebook.

Analytical Tools for Evaluation Pharmaceutical Treatment of Neurological Diseases – A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes implementation details of analytical method and conclusions of novel approach to clinical trials monitoring and pharmaceutical drugs evaluation [1]. The designed tools and implemented method utilizes mobile application and neural networks based algorithms for assisting and monitoring of time-constrained symptoms reporting. The research provides proofs that strict, assisted health state reporting correlated with sensor data acquisition can objectivize clinical trials therefore making the process more accurate. The designed algorithms are applied for wearable sensor data analysis in order to evaluate the intensity of tremor or dyskinesia and further to correlate the patient's survey data with acquired through sensors data. Based on clinical trials observations, a set of requirements for validating symptoms of neurological diseases have been formulated, concentrating on selected few, which can be registered using wearable biomedical sensors. The constructed tools utilize conventional surveying methods supplemented with biomedical sensor for neurological symptoms recognition and intensity evaluation. Developed mobile system is aimed at clinical trials assistance utilizing sensor-based state evaluation. Such quantitative approach is a supplement for patient's subjective evaluation of health state. This work is a discussion on pros and cons of such process composition and its supplementation with technology. Existing methodology relies on patient's health state evaluation based on iteratively answered questionnaires, which in our understanding cannot be fully controlled, thus reliable. The utilization of actigraphy and electromyography techniques [2] provides efficient means of some gestures recognition but most of all PD tremor identification and intensity evaluation, therefore can be used for ON/OFF state and dyskinesia identification and evaluation. In order to recognize specific states for PD patients (tremors, bradykinesias, rigidity, mental slowness, etc.) a set of additional techniques have been designed and implemented. The paper contains summary of research assumptions and validation results obtained during the conceptual and testing phase of a deployed IQPharma Clinical Trials Assistant system [1]. The original findings of presented research provide three correlating aspects (methods) of pharmaceutical therapy evaluation:

1. Patient subjective health state evaluation - based on the patient survey responses,
2. Tremor recognition and intensity evaluation – based on the inertial and biomedical sensor data analysis – aggregated features of actigraphy and electromyography
3. Reflex and mental perception assessment - based on the touch screen exercise evaluation and accuracy and providing complementary assessment of patient.

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Biomedical Sensors and Iot Platform Utilisation for Neurological Applications and Health Event Recognitions

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ABSTRACT

Biomedical monitoring is becoming a tool which can improve reliable and accurate medical diagnostic and health state evaluation. Mobile software and platforms are hosts for advanced health state monitoring systems, and recently are moving towards decision support tools. The analytical process must be supported by sensing equipment selected to evaluate specific symptoms (and preferably their intensity) of a given disease. This paper will discuss usage of surface multichannel electromyography and supplemented with arms activity evaluation. These data sources need to be selected with regard to not only detection accuracy but also mobility and usability features, which make the measuring process so cumbersome and difficult. In this work we summarise our effort to prepare the sensors, tune them to provide details on NERVE sensor, which has been based on IoT platform components and supplemented with MYO multi-sensor as a supplementary data source. Constructed system has been designed to consume electromyography and inertial data in order to feed seizure detection algorithms, responsible for health event detection and alarms. The application provides also novel approach in case of child seizures aimed not only at supporting parents but also at recording and assessing seizure symptoms. This work demonstrates signal processing algorithms, and describes functionality of designed system in the domain of hardware and software components. Recent advances in biomedical sensors and their popularity among users provide new ways of supplementing decision tools. Majority of available tools concentrate on data acquisition and simple aggregation, at most providing timeframe characteristics, however not evaluating the Electromyography (EMG) is a biopotential measuring technique, which can indirectly be used for investigating the central nervous system (CNS). In many diseases EMG reflects the activity of the spinal motoneurons due to motor units (MUs). In this work we seek a reliable method for recognition and identification of motor onset (both focal and generalised) seizures. This technique can be also applied to diagnose Parkinsons Disease [1][2]. In ideal, such method would also be helpful to detect PD either at early stage or even pre-clinically based on specific recognisable movement disorder patterns.

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Dynamic Façade Design based on Visual Comfort and Daylight Performance Optimization

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ABSTRACT

The building envelope plays an important role in the control of the natural daylight demand at a building scale. An optimized configuration of the façade can contribute to reduce in the total energy consumption of the building. Recently, there has been an increase in the work on responsive building facades, which can offer to increase indoor visual comfort while reducing energy consumption. In order to provide this, kinetic structures with foldable elements can be used to provide variation in the building envelope by motion.

In contrast to rigid shading elements, dynamic façade elements having different configurations can provide an effective solution for controlling solar radiation and daylight. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the main parameters determining the geometry and the kinematic behavior of dynamic shading elements based on loop-based method [1], and their effect on the performance as a shading system.

In this study, a shading module has been constructed by the loop-based method. The parametric model of the system has been modelled in Grasshopper® to evaluate the geometry of the building while providing the visual comfort of the interior. The parametric model generates the case building and the shading elements in a virtual environment. Two plug-ins for Grasshopper® (Ladybug and Honeybee) have been used to calculate the daylight performance. Since shading elements cover most of the facades, visual perception of the user in the interior space have been also calculated, as a counter objective. To simulate the visual comfort provided by each shading alternative, a geometry-based calculation method has been used within the software. Later, as a multi-objective evolutionary optimization tool, Octopus has been used to search for many goals at once and to produce optimized solutions for each goals to be satisfied by using Pareto-principle.

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Weight and Material Optimization of Scissor-hinge Structures According to the Various Span Lengths

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ABSTRACT

Scissor-hinge structures are one of the most common types of deployable structures because of their basic geometric/ motion principles and easy assembly details. For hundreds of years, these structures have been used in wide range of applications in architecture, and engineering as deployable roof structures, bridges, shells, furniture designs and satellite equipment.

Scissor-hinge structures have different primary elements depending on the geometry of the bars and the location of the pivot point called as “polar, translational and angulated” [1]. Geometry and dimensions of these primary elements directly affect the geometry of the whole structure as well as the cross sections of the bars.

This study aims to investigate the relationship between the span length, geometry of the primary units, cross section of the bars and the material for scissor-hinge structures with the help of genetic algorithms. In detail, a structural and geometric optimization is made in order to obtain the lightest geometric configuration for the given span lengths while keeping structural strength and stability by altering typology, dimensions and number of the primary units, material parameters of the problem. To achieve that multi objective genetic algorithm based optimization approach is utilized.

Generative model is created in Grasshopper parametric design software. The structural performances of generated solutions are evaluated with the help of Karamba3D that is a parametric structural tool for Grasshopper. Optimization of the problem is done via multi objective genetic optimization plug-in named Octopus.

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Optimizing the Use of Formalin Aqueous by Using Disposed Formalin Aqueous to Improve Properties of Expansive Soil

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ABSTRACT

With the recently increased interest for the sustainable engineering and its applications in geotechnical engineering, soil stabilization becomes a customary strategy used to enhance soils to accomplish the specifications of different projects.

Expansive soil (swelling –shrinking soil) will show a volume increase if exposed to water. This increase in volume will produce uplift pressure under the footing of the structure resting on it. As a result, a severe damage may cause to the structure if this type of soil is not treated to lower its expansive amount. Soil treatment, which includes soil stabilization by additives, is a well know method in this field. As a new technique, the addition of formalin aqueous waste (a mixture of chemicals known as *embalming fluid* and is used to preserve bodies of deceased persons for both funeral purposes and in medical research in anatomical laboratories), even at low doses, could improve the expansive soil properties. In the United States alone, about 20 million liters (roughly 5.3 million gallons) of embalming fluid are used, and consequently disposed, every year [1].

This paper describes a study on the possibility of using the disposed Formalin to improve the engineering properties of an expansive clayey-soil. To evaluate the strength characteristics of such expansive clayey soil, laboratory investigation on early strength gain of the stabilized soil was conducted on an expansive soil taken from the northern part of Jordan, Irbid city. To attain this target, the effect of used Formalin on swelling potential, maximum dry unite weight, and unconfined compressive strength of the expansive clay was examined in this study. The results showed that the formalin (embalming fluid) improves the engineering properties of the expansive soil used in this work.

Keywords: Expansive soil, Formalin, disposed, strength, swelling potential.

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Resonance Investigation and its Effects on Weight Optimization of Tubular Steel Wind Turbine Towers

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ABSTRACT

As attention on wind energy is progressively increasing, wind turbine towers grow in height and the blades become longer to better exploit the available wind potential. As a result, actions on the towers are also increased and their safe and cost-effective design is important for the further development of the wind energy sector. A commonly used type of wind turbine tower is the tubular steel tower, which offers several structural advantages and has dominated the market over other alternatives, such as truss-type towers. The tubular wind turbine tower is composed of a number of cylindrical and/or conical shells, manufactured in the factory and erected on site by means of bolted ring flange connections.

The objective of the presented research is to investigate and optimize an actual 120m tall tubular wind turbine tower with respect to resonance. The optimization's objective is to reduce weight, hence also cost, taking properly into account restrictions pertaining to fabrication, transportation and erection. According to pertinent recommendations, the tower's fundamental frequencies should not coincide with the rotor (1P) and blade-passing (3P) frequencies and should be kept outside specific ranges above and below these frequencies. For towers of such height avoidance of resonance becomes critical compared to other structural design checks, such as buckling and fatigue. Considering that the rotor and blades have predefined mass and rotation frequencies, the tower's fundamental frequencies should be controlled considering properly the cross-sectional properties of the tower over its height as well as the flexibility of the tower's foundation.

In the present investigation the vibration modes and frequencies of the tower are determined via more detailed as well as simplified finite element models with the latter proving to be sufficiently accurate. The dependence of the tower's vibration frequencies on the type and features of the foundation is also investigated. The above numerical models are incorporated into an optimization algorithm, aiming at minimizing the thickness of the tower shell over its height to optimize its weight without violating the resonance criteria.

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Coupling Shear Walls with Connecting Beams: An Investigation Based on Topology Optimization

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ABSTRACT

Coupled shear walls are often used to provide tall buildings with adequate resistance to lateral loads induced by wind or earthquake actions. Such wall systems essentially comprise of two or more solid walls, which are coupled by incorporating connecting beams at various elevations within the gaps between walls. The aim is to provide the connected walls with sufficient coupling effect to successfully withstand as a system the lateral loads under study. However, achieving the desired coupling effect in a cost-effective manner is not a straightforward task.

In the present work, the term ‘connecting beam’ is used in the more general sense of a ‘connecting structure’, as each link coupling shear walls may comprise of several structural segments. Thus, each ‘connecting beam’ may be a clearly identified beam-like link (as is typically the case in coupled shear walls), but it may alternatively consist of a network of connected sub-beams or a truss-like structure bridging the gap between the walls. It may sound enormously complicated to design such ‘connecting structures’, however this can be automatically handled within a topology optimization process.

By employing a topology optimization procedure, we can simultaneously determine in an automatic and optimal way: (a) the number of connecting beams/structures required to couple any number and configuration of solid walls, (b) the location (elevation) of each connecting beam/structure, (c) the topological characteristics of the structural segments comprising each ‘connecting structure’ and (d) the shape and cross-sectional geometry of each connecting beam/structure and corresponding structural segments.

A two-dimensional structural topology optimization procedure is implemented in this work to detect the optimum design of connecting beams/structures by minimizing the compliance (maximizing the global stiffness) of a coupled shear wall system under plane stress for a prescribed available coupling material volume. The design variables correspond to the material ‘density’ in each Finite Element (FE) of the discretized design domain between the plane stress walls. The final topology yielded reveals the optimum number, locations and characteristics of the required connecting beams/structures to couple the solid walls considered and leads to interesting overall external forms of coupled shear wall systems. A number of design cases with various shear wall configurations are examined to demonstrate the applicability and appreciate the significance of the presented topology optimization procedure.

1st International Conference on Optimization Driven Architectural Design

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Applications of Parametric Design in Architecture – Advantages and Disadvantages

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ABSTRACT

During the last two decades parametric design method has been widely used in architecture. At the beginning people were attracted by the sculptural fancy forms as results of using parametric design. However, the use of parametric technology was not limited to only producing attractive forms, but it was also applied to achieve optimal solutions in other aspects such as structural, environmental, economic and construction issues.

Despite the ongoing discussion and debate among architects regarding the advantages and disadvantages of using parametric design in architecture, it is believed that it has more benefits than just creating complex and unusual forms. Parametric architecture became a new trend for many architects worldwide. Internationally renowned architects have used parametric technology in many different ways for different purposes. Projects designed by Zaha Hadid Architects (ZHA), Frank Gehry, Ma Yansong (MAD), Tom Wiscombe, and LAVA architects, are often used as examples to illustrate the applications of parametric design in architecture.

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate and discuss the work of some prominent architects known for their use of parametric method in their design, in order to show the different approaches and applications of this method in architecture. Based on material obtained directly from “parametric” architects, examples of their work will be used as case studies for comparison to find out the different approaches, and to highlight and demonstrate the advantages and disadvantages of using parametric technology in their designs.

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Charpy Impact Testing (High Strain Rate) Can Detect the Presence of Hydrogen in High Strength Steels

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen was intentionally introduced into ultra-high strength steel by cadmium plating. The purpose was to examine the effect of cadmium plate thickness, and hence, hydrogen content on the Charpy Impact toughness of the steel. The AISI 4340 steel was austenitized at 1000 °C for 1 hour, water quenched, and tempered at temperatures between 494 and 1100 °C in order to achieve a range of targeted strength levels. The specimens were cadmium plated with 0.00508mm (0.2 mils), 0.00762mm (0.3 mils), and 0.0127mm (0.5 mils). Results demonstrated that the uncharged specimens exhibited higher impact energy values when compared to the plated specimens at all tempering temperatures. The results of this work are best explained by the “Dislocation Transport (Sweeping) of Hydrogen” model.

Keywords: 4340 Steel, Charpy Impact Test, Hydrogen Charging, Cadmium Plating

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Architectural and Structural Optimization Research of Structural Forms Topologically Transformed

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ABSTRACT

In nature, homologues can be seen in structures of common evolutionary origin, which are composed of similar elements in the same zones. Homology shows the relationship of living organisms, which may differ externally, but their structure (bone and muscle) is characterized by significant similarity. The equivalent of homologous transformations in mathematics is homeomorphism, which is one of the basic concepts of the department of contemporary mathematics dealing with the study of the properties of topological geometric figures and solids (properties which do not change even after radical continuous deformation of figures), called topology. Homeomorphism is about transforming figures without tearing them apart and gluing them together, only by stretching, compressing, bending and twisting them, which enables continuity and identity functions to be maintained. Homeomorphic spaces are indistinguishable from the point of view of topology. Homeomorphism of space ensures the preservation of topological invariables, which include a number of features such as closeness, openness, compactness, centrality or cohesion. Optimization searches for solids based on topological transformations, carried out in the scope of architectural and structural criteria can be an important element of analyses in the interdisciplinary design process. On their basis it is possible to make a conscious choice between individual forms inspired by geometry or structures found in nature. The paper presents the results of model analyses of structural forms formed on the basis of topological transformations with determination of their effectiveness in terms of minimum mass. Optimization searches due to the minimum mass are an important element from the design of objects due to the idea of sustainable development.

Diagrid Systems Coupled with Closed- and Open-Section Shear Walls: Optimization of Geometrical Characteristics in Tall Buildings

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays diagrid systems are employed worldwide for the realization of tall buildings since they allow to achieve remarkable architectural effects while providing an efficient mechanism to limit lateral displacements. Furthermore, being composed by an assembly of trusses on the exterior of the structure, they are suitable for optimization procedures if changing geometrical parameters, such as the inclination of the external diagonals [1]. Such optimization procedures are generally carried out by means of Finite Element models, focusing mostly on diagrid lateral rigidity.

In the last few decades, in order to perform the structural analysis of tall buildings made up of different resisting elements, an analytical formulation, called General Algorithm (GA), was developed [2], which is much less time-consuming than FE calculations, while allowing to capture important insights on the structural behavior [3]. Moreover, a matrix-based method has been recently proposed for the analysis of diagrid systems, which was shown to be suitable for insertion into the GA and able to provide information on the diagrid lateral and torsional flexibility as well [4].

In this contribution, we analyze the structural behavior of external diagrid systems coupled with closed- and open-section shear walls using the GA. The analysis was performed by considering lateral forces and torque moments distributed along the height of the building. By the GA, defined the building height and plan geometry, the optimal inclination of the external diagonals was sought, in order to minimize both lateral displacements and torsional rotations. Moreover, the effect of the shear wall type, i.e. closed- or open-section, was investigated on the structural response, and it was found to have a significant impact on the torsional rotations. Eventually, a multi-parameter approach is briefly presented in order to account for variable inclinations of the diagonals along the height of the building.

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Measurement Models of Information Security Based on the Principles and Practices for Risk-Based Approach

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ABSTRACT

Elements of good practice and principles of a risk-based approach are often used in measurement models to assess the level of security of the information resource. The practical problem of measuring the level of risk in information security is the selection of an appropriate model, followed by measures (indicators) and a method that will be adequate to the specific organization, and as a result will give the best basis for establishing system solutions, in particular will allow the selection of effective safeguards (countermeasures) for individual information resources. The article presents two models proposed by authors and two refinements of models most often used in practice. In order to obtain comparable and reproducible results of measuring the level of security of the information resource, assumptions related to the adopted definition of security as well as the definition of risk and its measure were adopted for each model. The proposed by authors models can become the starting point for creating an information security evaluation system for each type of organization.

Research methodology

The research methods used are: studies of professional literature, analysis of EU legal provisions, as well as a critical analysis of the definition of risk and security of information resources of the examined organizational units, in entities processing documents with different levels of sensitivity.

Key findings

The four models of measuring the level of security of information resources presented in the article are focused on the application of risk-based principles and practices. Each of these models considers the assumptions regarding the definition of the security of the information resource, its context and how to measure information security. In addition, it gives the opportunity to choose different areas of the organization and a set of risk factors relating to threats and vulnerabilities occurring in individual phases of the life cycle of the information resource and binding them in a manner allowing for the full and unambiguous determining of the risk level in information security, while maintaining the practical usefulness of the proposed approaches.

Novelty & scientific value

The proposed models were used to develop the framework structure of the risk management system and relevant policies, in particular the information security policy in the audited organizational unit, in which the level of information resources security was measured with different levels of sensitivity using the developed models. The usefulness of the measurement models presented in this article has also been confirmed as part of the seminar on its theoretical and practical aspects.

Risk Based Approach in Scope of Cyber Security Threats and Requirements

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ABSTRACT

Paper is focused on theoretical and practical considerations related to risk management in organizations whose are going to implement security mechanisms to align with the in force requirements or to reduce cyber threats to accepted level. The process of risk analysis was introduced by authors and is followed with the description of the example risk evaluation method for the hypothetical organization.

Research methodology

The research methods used are: literature studies, analysis of the polish law in scope of the national cyber security system, analysis of guidelines, directives and codes in cyber security and development of modern technologies in the context of building the Digital Single Market, as well as critical analysis and assessment of currently used risk management methods in scope of the cyber threats of the organization.

Key findings

The main result of scientific work is the proposition of the risk of cyber threats analysis and assessment model. This model is followed with the description of the example of cyber threats risk estimation and evaluation method for the hypothetical organization. The model takes into account various categories of cyber threats and risk factors relevant to the proper functioning of the organization and ensuring the completeness of the process of determining the level of risk in relation to organization's critical assets. Proposed method is composed with the: (1) method of risk analysis, and (2) method of risk management. They have been combined together to allow for the full and unambiguous determination of the risk level in scope of the organization's cyber security. Practical usability of the proposed approach was key factor during its design, as well. Measurement of the organization's security level is based on the estimation and monitoring of cyber threats and the level of risk. Exposition to the cyber threats is related with use of the organization's assets in the aspect of providing them with security attributes (i.e. confidentiality, accessibility, non-repudiation, accountability, reliability and integrity of information).

Novelty & scientific value

The cyber security should be considered as multilevel, non-monolithic and multifaceted phenomenon. It's influence on modern organizations could be analyzed at different levels and with use of the various approaches. This paper addresses the many dimensions of the organization's cyber threats for its various key areas of activity and cyber security approaches. The way of its presentation was designated by the gradation of threats from the internal level through external to global manifestations (e.g. challenges for information security or functional security, cyber-espionage, information fight, or cyber terrorism). The article may fill the gap associated with a very modest literature items analyzing the risk of cyber threats in a holistic way. The usefulness of the risk management methodology presented in this paper in the aspect of cyber threats has also been identified as a part of the seminar on its theoretical and practical aspects.

The Importance of the Integrated Security System for Critical Infrastructure Operation and Safety

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ABSTRACT

The paper is focused on theoretical and practical aspects concerning the role of the IT elements of the integrated security system in the process of maintaining nor increasing the level of security related to the critical infrastructure (CI). Concept of a package of the IT tools proposed herein allows for the implementation of the integrated security system. Role of this system is to increase the effectiveness of detecting, counteracting and neutralizing the effects of cyber threats for the CI. Authors refer to the tasks of the units who are responsible for cyber security of the CI. These tasks are arranged around the three dimensions: technology, organization and processes. They are considered to be a substantial part of the processes of: maintaining the critical infrastructure operations continuity, eliminating of a SPOF, separating critical infrastructure elements from the outside world and raising awareness.

Research methodology

The research methods used are: literature studies, review of recent standards, critical analysis of the solutions applicable within the critical infrastructure security systems, document research, interviews and surveys with professionals in the field of construction and implementation of critical infrastructure.

Key findings

The main result of scientific work is the proposal of the integrated security system of the critical infrastructure. The set of its elements contains three groups of solutions: Information Technology (IT), Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Operational Technology (OT). Proper operation of elements in these groups is substantial for the critical infrastructure safety and its protection. The essential differences between these solutions, important for effective protection of the critical infrastructure, have been introduced in this paper. Different areas of applications for IT, ICT and OT solutions cause dissimilarity in the perception of security aspects between them. Considering the security perspective of an IT and an ICT solution it is crucial to ensure confidentiality, integrity, accountability and non-repudiation of data and business processes. While for an OT solution, the most important is to ensure reliability, availability and continuity of the production process.

Novelty & scientific value

Various types of changes that could occur in the modern environment of integrated security solutions of the critical infrastructure have been analyzed. Different types and groups of threats have been distinguished. Effective protection of critical infrastructure seems to have primarily concern a process of maintaining the integrity and continuity of processes that the infrastructure directly provides or indirectly supports in the chain of related activities with external structures.

Models and Methods for Measurement of Risk Management System Usability

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ABSTRACT

Systematization of issues related to the approach to defining and measuring the usefulness of a risk management system in information security is one of the key milestones on the way to understand it. Therefore, a number of existing models and methods used in this area were critically analyzed. Authors attempted to modify and improve them, basing on the results of in-depth studies carried out by themselves in multiple organizations. The paper presents the results of attempts to adapt selected models and methods of risk analysis to the requirements that allow their use in the field of cyber security.

Research methodology

The research methods used are: literature studies, analysis of standards, guidelines, directives and codes in cyber security, critical analysis and assessment of currently used in Europe methods of measuring the usefulness of a risk management systems, document research, interviews and surveys with professionals in the field of construction and implementation of a risk management systems.

Key findings

The main result of scientific work are the concept and the approach to defining the usability of the risk management system. Paper provides results in three key areas covering: modeling of the usability attributes of a risk management system, methods of usability testing (quantitative and qualitative) and methods of measuring selected properties of the risk management system. The results shows that the risk management systems must have specific functional properties that determine such attributes as: functionality, purposefulness, rationality, efficiency, effectiveness, and above all reliability and security.

Novelty & scientific value

This does not cover all issues related to the measurement of the usefulness of risk management systems in information security. Topic is quite often overlooked in the professional literature and there is weak availability of publications concerning this aspects. The outcome of this paper is to address needs of practitioners of information security, who want to deepen knowledge on the issues of measuring and monitoring the usefulness of implemented risk management systems or information security management systems.

Data-Driven Machine Learning System for Optimization of Processes Supporting the Distribution of Goods and Services – a case study

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the concept of a machine-learning system (Distribution Optimization System (DOS)) increasing the efficiency of the process of supporting the distribution of goods and services. The elements of the presented concept are geocoding algorithms (i.e. precise calculation of the delivery address, based on the transmitted information), route calculation algorithms (solving the modified VRPTW problem with large size in stochastic time-dependent networks) and distribution region optimization algorithms, as well as smart tracking device monitoring vehicle traffic parameters, characterized by extremely long autonomous operation time (on batteries) and resistance to GPS interference.

The existing models and solutions in Intelligent Transportation Systems do not fully use a few possibilities offered by the quickly developing information technologies, optimization algorithms, artificial intelligence (AI), Including Machine Learning (ML), Internet of Things (IoT). To optimize logistic processes, it is required to include the solutions combined with the parameters that may be derived from global/mass data (Big Data) within a given area, organization/enterprise specific historical data, additional support with the results generated by the machine learning AI algorithms, based on the described flow of input data. Therefore, the main results of the research being presented, which differ from existing solutions, is concept of a machine-learning system for optimization distribution of goods and services. The essence of the project is to use the collected data from distribution process for continued learning and improvement of the system's operations.

The Distribution Optimization System (DOS) shall translate directly into the following: reduction of exploitation costs, including costs of devices, i.e. means of transport, fuel, use of human resources; optimization of resource use while planning and organizing logistics processes; facilitation of implementation of eco-friendly solutions, including optimization of routes, time and moment of their use.

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Evaluation of Service Effectiveness of Bus Transit Routes Using Data Envelopment Analysis Model in Irbid, Jordan

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ABSTRACT

Public transit is a strong index for the development of any city. It has an essential role in developing the socio-economic and environmental sides. Limited researches were conducted to measure service effectiveness of bus routes, taking into account the uncontrolled operational environment. Making it easier for decision makers to find out whether route's deficiency resulted mainly from agency decisions or from the operational environment which may have a negative impact on the route's performance. This study evaluates the service effectiveness of bus lines of Irbid city, Jordan using Data Envelopment Analysis model.

The weak effectiveness of the existing public transit services in terms of frequency, availability, on time performance and capacity and the limited existing resources is a problem that many developing countries suffer from. So there is a need to a suitable method that helps in finding the most needed routes for the improvement which is the data envelopment analysis model that used in this research, which help in the allocation of the existing resources in their right place. The inputs that used to apply in this model is the seat kilometers and the outputs are ridership, frequency and maximum frequency. These variables are applied in the model after removing the marginal effects of the selected environmental variables existing within the buffer zone (population density and car ownership) which suppose to affect the effectiveness of Irbid city internal transit routes. The service effectiveness resulted scores of most routes were inefficient and the environmental factors doesn't have a great effect on the route's performance which indicates that deficiency resulted from agency decisions so agency needs to reschedule the public transit routes to mitigate congestion problems and its consequences.

Keywords: service effectiveness evaluation, bus routes, data envelopment analysis model, environmental variables

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A Modified Semi-Probabilistic Approach for the Assessment of the Residual Service Life of Concrete Structures Subjected to Carbonation

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ABSTRACT

Service life estimation using a probabilistic performance-based design is currently gaining attention from researchers, designing engineers as well as business owners. Common application is, unfortunately, prevented by insufficient dissemination of basic ideas, relevant knowledge or experimental evidence, and by lack of simple, user friendly and yet efficient design tools (software and others)[1]. This paper presents a modification on an existing semi-probabilistic model that is used for the estimation of the residual service life of reinforced concrete structures subjected to corrosion due to carbonation. The existing model is applied on a low-sample scope data that is normally distributed. Matlab Codes were developed for the estimation of the residual service life of reinforced concrete structures subjected to carbonation corrosion with normal and non-normal probability distributions through the application of reliability analysis using Hasofer-Lind method for normally distributed variables and Rackwitz-Fiessler method for non-normal variables. Monte Carlo simulation were also performed to validate the results of the modified model and to produce a practical approach for the determination of the residual service life without the need for deep background in probability and statistics. The modified model was validated using existing data available in literature and is expected to serve as an efficient and user-friendly design tool that is able to deliver an estimation of the residual service life of carbonated reinforced concrete structures.

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Mathematical Models of Information Operations

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ABSTRACT

The changes occurring in the contemporary world are related to the dynamics of the development of modern technologies and its impact on life of almost every person. Currently, as never before in human history, “everything is interconnected” through ICT networks and systems, creating the so-called cyberspace. An important issue is the fact that cyberspace constitutes a part of the information environment of modern man and, thanks to popularization of social media, it is treated as the new social sphere where people “meet”.

The new space – cyberspace – used to perform Cyber Operations (*CyberOps*) and to a larger extent Information Operations (*InfoOps*) has significant impact on potential risks to the public security, existing both at the technical and informational level. The “wars of the future” will be mainly carried out in cyberspace. Additionally, the “traditional” Cyber Operations will be more and more often synchronized with the Information Operations, creating de facto one collective operation in cyberspace. The battlefield will be information and data processing systems, thus, not only hard ICT infrastructure (*CyberOps*), but everything that is “connected” thereto, including people – i.e. “brains realizing cognitive processes” (*InfoOps*). Due to wide access to the Internet, social media started to play more significant role in the shaping of public opinion on basically every subject and to broadly impact the way of world perception by people, social groups or whole societies.

In the paper, particular emphasis is put on discussing mathematical models of information operations seeing that: theory of reflexive control, theory of disinformation, game theory or hypergame theory. The main issue in case of the modeling of information operations in social media is to understand the dissemination (diffusion) process of the phenomena in this environment, including assessment of the role and significance of particular “nodes” in the network and forecast of diffusion dynamics and reach of the information being a product of the information operation.

Current studies presented in the paper, center, around the consistent model of information operations based on the theory of reflective control, game theory and hypergame theory (quantitative approach), disinformation theory (qualitative approach) and at the same time has regard to models of diffusion of phenomena in network systems.

Best of Both Worlds – Using Computational Design and Deep Learning for Real-Time Urban Performance Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

The urgency of climate change and the significant contribution of buildings to it have been leading the recent shift to performance driven design in the AEC industry. Despite constant efforts for the incorporation of building performance simulation tools in current design workflows, they still suffer from demanding timeframes due to computational demands and lack of domain knowledge by designers. The main objective of this study is to assess the potential of Deep Learning (DL) in Computational Environmental Design (CED) workflows, specifically at the urban scale, bringing together two until now disparate domains of practice in order to close the gap between performance feedback and design in the early stages of urban design projects. Achieving real-time performance feedback can be instrumental for a properly informed early design process as well as in enabling the exploration of the unprecedentedly large design spaces evident in the complex design problems we face in the real world. This study proposes a Deep Learning (DL) approach for the prediction of Solar Radiation (SR) performance. The selection of SR as the performance indicator was driven by the low computational demands involved in SR simulations and by the established and validated state-of-the-art simulation engines available. This allowed us to generate large datasets, in a logical time frame, without the need to question the accuracy and efficiency of the results. A different but equally important advantage of using SR as a proxy is that it represents a first step towards other, more complex and much more valuable performance evaluations such as Thermal Comfort and Renewable Energy potential. The software stack involved in this study can be split into two functional parts: (i) Computational Design Tools and (ii) Deep Learning Models and Libraries. The first part took place exclusively within the Rhinoceros and Grasshopper (GH) environments. Ladybug Tools were used to simulate SR for each geometrical input, using the ray-tracing capabilities of Radiance. The popular DL library PyTorch was used for the development and training of the DL models involved. We trained multiple models for 8 different cities around the world, 7 in the U.S. and one in Europe (Vienna), with one model trained for each location. This allowed us to assess the capacity of the model across different geographical locations, climate conditions, massing complexity and diversity. Results showed that the models generate extremely accurate predictions of SR on previously unseen massing configurations, which indicates that they have generalized well, that is captured the relationship between urban context, climatic conditions, and SR performance. In order to assess the role of these models in developing an intelligent design decision support framework, GH scripts with custom Python components were developed allowing us to deploy the models and generate real time SR predictions for arbitrary urban massing within GH. The framework was shown to several users who were allowed to experiment and produce their own results, giving us an idea as to how real-time performance prediction might alter the user's perspective and choices during early-stage design. We are currently in the process of developing a multi-city dataset that will span most important locations around the globe. This will also allow us to test our ability to generalize across locations by seeing if it is possible to train a context and location independent model for prediction of SR at the urban scale. This is only the first step towards more complex, and far more time-consuming assessments such as wind flow and thermal comfort prediction.

Software Architecture Optimization of Mobile Biomedical Sensor-Based Tools Providing Analytical Services for Disease Diagnostics and Assistance

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ABSTRACT

The development of highly specialized mobile applications and systems has risen for several years, as we observe rapid deployment of innovative biomedical sensors and wearable technologies. The experiences gathered over 10 years of mobile medical software development, provide practical recommendations for architectural concepts utilized in analytical health-based services. Constructed systems and mobile applications in majority cases utilize biomedical signals to identify health state of a patient [1], as well as to evaluate or estimate the intensity of disease symptoms. Based on these experiences, this paper proposes architectural concepts, for both mobile and web-based components aimed at acquisition and processing of biomedical data in large scale medical systems dedicated for patient monitoring. The major assumptions for this research included utilization of wearable and mobile technologies, supporting maximum number of wearable diagnostic technologies including inertial and biomedical data streams. Although medical diagnostics and decision algorithms have not been the main aim of the research, this preliminary phase was crucial to test capabilities of existing off-the-shelf technologies and functional responsibilities of system's logic components. Optimized architecture variants contain several schemes [1] for data processing, moving the responsibility for signal feature extraction, data classification and pattern recognition from wearable to mobile application and further to server services. Recommendations for hosting specific algorithms The analysis of delays during data transmission and processing, provided architecture variants' pros and cons but most of captured recommendations for applicability of such mechanisms in the domains of medical, military and fitness. To evaluate and construct architecture, a set of alternative technology stacks and quantitative measures has been defined. The major architecture characteristics (high availability, scalability, reliability) have been defined imposing asynchronous processing of sensor data, efficient data representation, iterative reporting, event-driven processing, restricting pulling operations. Analytical processing of inertial or biomedical sensor data requires filtering, time-window processing, aggregation, application of specific algorithmic transformations etc. Combination of several data sources and correlation of biomedical parameters between each other and specific patient's health state, extend predefined ordinarily used event triggering rules. This work provides construction details of wearable-based mobile systems with specialized aimed at health state identification and monitoring. Undertaken construction decisions have been confirmed and justified based on functional and stress tests of system components. The first deployment attempt of designed architecture and its implementation has been aimed at remote, mobile monitoring of elderly people, and preconfigured for crucial health event recognition – fainting, stroke, cardiac arrest, seizures, some classes of neurological disorders [2] and derivatives of such conditions.

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Topology Optimization in Acoustics and Elasto-Acoustics via a Level-Set Method

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ABSTRACT

Optimizing the shape and topology (S&T) of structures to improve their acoustic performance is quite challenging. The exact position of the structural boundary is usually of critical importance, which dictates the use of geometric methods for topology optimization instead of standard density approaches. The goal of the present work is to investigate different possibilities for handling topology optimization problems in acoustics and elasto-acoustics via a level-set method. From a theoretical point of view, we detail two equivalent ways to perform the derivation of surface-dependent terms and propose a smoothing technique for treating problems of boundary conditions optimization. In the numerical part, we examine the importance of the surface-dependent term in the shape derivative, neglected in previous studies found in the literature, on the optimal designs. Moreover, we test different mesh adaptation choices, as well as technical details related to the implicit surface definition in the level-set approach. We present results in two and three-space dimensions.

Behavior of Prefabricated Full-Depth Precast Concrete Bridge Deck Panel System: Optimum Prestress Level

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on results and findings obtained from a non-linear finite element analysis (NLFEA) of a prototype prefabricated full-depth precast concrete bridge deck panel system under different level of prestress force. The NLFEA were validated with experimental results obtained from full-scale testing of the prototype bridge system. The benefits of the NLFEA can be highly appreciated when visualizing the substantial time and cost savings, the ability to change any parameter of interest, and the capability of demonstrating any interesting response at any load value and at any location in the system. The most attractive results were: (1) the system is capable of withstanding and maintaining its integrity under eight times the simulated AASHTO truck service load without considerable reduction in its ultimate strength capacity and stiffness, (2) The NLFEA showed that the live load-induced bond stresses for 4 lines prestress level was almost 0.74 times the live load-induced bond stresses for 6 lines prestress level.

Optimization of Multi-type Sensor Locations for Simultaneous Estimation of Link Travel Times and Origin-Destination Demands

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ABSTRACT

Sensor locations optimization for origin-destination (OD) estimation demand has been widely used such as in transportation management and intelligent transportation system. Sensors originally located for OD estimation can also provide additional information for link travel time estimation that is traditionally based on single source data. However, different types of sensors have been and will be located on the road networks. To make full use of the information acquired from multi-type sensors, a modified generalized least square (M-GLS) model for network-wide simultaneous estimation of OD demands and link travel times is proposed in this study. Furthermore, a bi-criteria model is proposed to optimize multi-type sensor locations, then to enhance the estimation accuracy of both link travel times and OD demands. The application and efficiency of these two proposed models are demonstrated by a numerical example on a selected road network in Hong Kong.

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Virtual Reality-Neural Networks for reconstruction of devastated cities by earthquakes: lacustrine deposits in Mexico City

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ABSTRACT

The reconstruction of a city that has been devastated by an earthquake requires the intelligent management of resources and the establishment of work directions that return, as quickly as possible, the largest number of inhabitants to their routine life. The most important difficulty arising in the initial reconstruction after strong earthquakes period is to find the best assignment of available resources to operational areas. One of the aspects that must be taken care of immediately is the recovery of buried facilities that conduct water, gas or hydrocarbons. For solving this problem a dynamic optimization model is introduced. The model uses detailed 4D-descriptions of the regions with i) higher vulnerability to collapse, break or smash pipelines, ii) specific characteristics of the ground motions and the properties of soils deposits, iii) strategic densities of superstructures and inhabitants, iv) operational areas and v) available resources to calculate the resource performance and efficiency for different tasks related to the response.

To show the model capabilities, the September 19, 2017, M 7.1 earthquake in Central Mexico, occurred as the result of normal faulting, is used as an application example. At least 230 people killed at Mexico City and more than 5,000 people resulted injured. The authorities of this capital had to attend the call of 230 sites in which collapses were registered and more than six thousand in which the damages required the intervention of construction specialists. Based on a specialized *geo-datamart* and a Virtual Reality¹ – Neural Networks² framework (where the causes-effects can be simulated), the analysts define the regions where the complex geotechnical-earthquake-infrastructure interaction is more dangerous and the effect of associated damage such as leaks of dangerous substances (water and gas), could be devastating due to the number of people living in the surrounding area.

The spatial variation of geotechnical properties and the associated seismic responses are established with a dynamic-neural procedure while the millions of neuro-generated cause-effects links are used to feed a Virtual Reality engine that facilitates the intuitively visual understanding of the damage to pipelines and the posterior regionalization of the attention necessities. The versatility of the model allows the analyst to reconfigure the works based on reports of solved cases or new notifications of damages.

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Multi Criteria Evaluation for Sustainable Urban Growth in An-Nuayyimah, Jordan; Post War Study

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ABSTRACT

The problem of rapid urbanization is one of the most important problems that is threatening agricultural areas. The urban areas during their growth abolish many of the agricultural lands with high fertility value. During the last ten years, An-Nuayyimah town lost many agricultural lands as a consequence of this sprawl. In addition, the nearby region suffered from political instability which in turn led to thousands of Syrians seeking refuge in this town in particular. The population increased from 14,583 in 2010 to 29,128 in 2015. Historically, the stability of political and economic situation and the hospitality of the laws in Jordan encouraged all previous refugees to stay and get settled. Therefore, this study aims to define the most suitable areas for potential urban growth to suite the sudden spike population by integrating Geographical Information System (GIS) and Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE). Four criteria were used for urban growth evaluation which includes: Slope, land fertility, distance to an urban center, and distance to road. The final suitability map identifies four levels for suitability: Very High (area=3.13 km²), High (area=5.53 km²), Moderate (area= 3.35 km²), and Low (area=0.19 km²). In the end, two categories were selected (Very High suitability and High suitability) as the areas most suited for sustainable future urban growth.

Keywords: Suitability analysis; urban sprawl; multi-criteria evaluation; planning; developing countries; Irbid.

An Ontology for Multi Disciplinary Building Design Optimization

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ABSTRACT

The design of buildings requires the collaboration of many disciplines. Each of these disciplines has their own aims, unique knowledge, perspectives and design processes. It therefore follows that they have different ideas about which factors should be optimized. An alternative view is to view these different ideas as potential tradeoffs. There are many examples of optimized tradeoffs in nature such as supply and support in trees for instance. However projects in the built environment are typically less optimized than their analogues in the natural environment. In the built environment each disciplinary system is typically designed in its own disciplinary silo. It therefore follows that the optimizations also occur within these silos.

This paper identifies the potential optimization factors in a complex multi disciplinary project and the tradeoffs of the factors between the disciplines. For instance the relationship between the supply of space as controlled by the architectural discipline and the structural support of the supplied spaces from the structural engineers.

This is discussed using the example of a course at [omitted for peer review] that we have run a course for the last 10 years called Advanced Building Design. Around 90 civil and architectural engineering students participate in the course are divided into teams of 6. Each team member represents one of disciplines. This means that the students have to develop a building from the perspective of their own discipline whilst being aware of the needs of the other disciplines.

This case study provides an opportunity to consider the optimization of architectural design, it shows that there are many different factors that the team could optimize. To address this challenge, this paper documents an approach to develop an ontology multi disciplinary optimization of the building design. The paper does not intend to demonstrate how to implement the different optimizations but rather how to model the space of potential optimizations for the design team in the form of an ontology for multi-disciplinary building design.

To address this, it is important to define the scope of the ontology. To do this we could consider the potential use case. For instance if a member of the design team wanted to optimize the design to meet factors for a standard this would require that the ontology could include standards. Furthermore, if the design team wanted to optimize the design for specific materials it would require knowledge about those specific materials. These examples motivated us to include relevant standards and materials in the ontology. In its current form the ontology is optimized for its use in the university but through its basis on standards it is intended that in the future it will be possible to use it on real projects.

The main contribution of the paper is an extension of Arto Kiviniemi's work on developing a single requirements model that disciplines can then check their design models against. This would support the optimization process and could also be extended to include a separation of for instance spatial proposals and material solutions, to further aid not just the optimization process but the ability of the design team to test and optimize different options. These issues and others are discussed in this paper and the ontology is presented to support a discussion on the future of this approach and its implications on optimization in building design.

Analysing the Thermal Response of Perforated Masonry Walls under Thermal Actions on Structures Exposed To Fire

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyse and assess the thermal response of insulated masonry-walls formed with fired clay hollow bricks under thermal actions on structures exposed to fire corresponding to the standard temperature-time curve (nominal curve representing a model of a fully developed fire in a compartment; as defined in EN 1991-1-2). In this respect, two types of insulation materials that are widely used have been examined (expanded polystyrene and rock wool) to underline the impact of the flammability and fire resistance of this layer. In addition, the analysis has been extended to reveal the effect of the insulation layer position and thickness. Nevertheless, the significance of this investigation relies on the consideration of heat transfer mechanisms through a composite system (non-homogenous building configuration) with air cavities. Accordingly, the transient thermal analysis has been carried out by assuming different values of the emissivity at the surrounding surfaces within the air cavity region of hollow bricks. As it is clear, the effectiveness of surfaces in emitting energy affects critically the evolution of the heat wave due to fire. To accomplish this a well-known finite element software (COMSOL Multiphysics) has been utilized. Results of this study underline the importance to determine the thermal resistance of building components in aspect of the explicit geometry and properties of building materials forming their structure. In particular, special attention has been implicated to verify reliably the ability of various perforated masonry walls to restrict the temperature rise of the unexposed surface above 140 oC (insulation criterion, I). Taking into account the recent trend toward a performance based design practice of building structures against thermal actions and fires, the appraisal of this criterion in an integral part of a rational building design associated with fire safety engineering. In conclusion, the main goal of this work is to restrict unnecessary costs of construction and optimize building design without compromising safety due to fire risk.

Keywords: thermal actions, standard temperature-time curve, thermal resistance, perforated masonry walls, insulation flammability, hollow brick emissivity.

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Some Structural Design Issues on a Timber Bridge for Pedestrians

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ABSTRACT

The use of wood in timber bridges is increased over the past 20 years, mainly since wood is a renewable and sustainable resource. Nevertheless wood is a natural engineering material that is prone to deterioration caused by decay fungi, insect attack and temperature [1]. For wood and wooden bridges there is in fact a strong correlation between durability of the material and bearing capacity. Deformations in a timber structure are often a good indicator of the structural condition.

Within this context, in this study some structural issues dealing with the design of a timber bridge for pedestrians are investigated.

In a first step, the bridge shape is designed taking into account various aspects: timber as a bridge material; properties of structural wood products; rail systems for preservation and protection; wearing surfaces for timber decks in order to ensure durability; static and dynamic loads; static scheme [2]. In a second step, the bridge shape is optimized by a procedure based on the calibration of natural modes of vibration [2, 3].

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Optimal Pre-Stressed Arches Shapes with Variable Section Subject to Vertical Live Loads and Self-Weight

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ABSTRACT

In structural engineering beams with non-constant cross-section or beams of variable cross-section are represents a class of slender bodies, object of the practitioners interest due to the possibility of optimizing their geometry with respect to specific needs. Despite the advantages that engineers can obtain from their use, non-trivial difficulties occurring in the non-prismatic beam modeling often lead to inaccurate predictions that vanish the gain of the optimization process. As a consequence, an effective non-prismatic beam modeling still represents a branch of the structural engineering of interest for the community, especially for advanced design applications in large spans elements.

A straight beam of length l with variable inertia $J(z)$ is provided in figure, subject to a generic live load condition $q(z)$.

The vertical displacement $y(z)$ can be obtained from the solution of the differential equation of the elastic line, i.e., taking into consideration the inertia variability and neglecting, as first approximation, any shear contribution. Even if this solution is an approximate one, it is able to deal with the problem in its basic formulation.

In this paper a solution for the problem stated is formulated using a series expansion of solutions, in a general load and cross section variability condition.

Solution is thus obtained for a generic rectangular cross section beam with a variable height. Analytical solution is presented and evaluated using numerical evaluation of some cases of practical interest.

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Optimal Pre-Stressed Arches Shapes with Variable Section Subject to Vertical Live Loads and Self-Weight

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new analytical solution for the optimal shape of a plane statically determined arch subjected to uniform vertical loads is presented. The classical problem of a catenary subjected to the self-weight is extended to an inverted catenary subject to the self-weight and to a pre-stress load N_0 applied along the central axis of the arch's cross section, using the adoption of a variable cross section hypothesis. The optimal shape/section variation is, thus, obtained finding class of solutions able to minimize total volume (or self-weight) in the specific condition of a constant normal stress level for each sections. In this way, the material structural efficiency is maximized. Finally, a semi analytical solution is obtained for the class of problems dealing with a symmetric uniform vertical load.

The application condition for a class of analytical solutions already exists and, unlike previous proposed solutions, it corresponds to the minimum ratio of the self-weight of the arch on the total applied load under different pre stress loads.

Volume Optimization of Perfectly-Constrained Arches

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ABSTRACT

Arch arised as structural system more than two thousand years ago, but, in spite of this, it is still not widely diffused and is mainly adopted in presence of large spans. The structural efficiency of arches primarily depends on optimal material exploitation, i.e. minimization of internal stress eccentricity that reduces structural material volume and weight. An efficient structure, under these terms, leads to simple and light scaffolding, so contributing in minimizing construction costs. So, although literature on arches is already significant, there is still scope for design optimization. This study is framed within this context and deals with the structural analysis of end perfectly-constrained plane circular arches under uniformly distributed vertical load and self weight. In the first step, the analytical solution of arch static and kinematic behaviour is obtained by applying the force method. In the second step, the arch shape is optimized, by assuming the arch volume, and thus the weight, as objective function. Finally minima of the objective function (i.e. optimal geometric shape parameters) are computed and plotted in order to be used for practical purposes. The vertical displacement $y(z)$ can be obtained from the solution of the differential equation of the elastic line, i.e., taking into consideration the inertia variability and neglecting, as first approximation, any shear

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Optimal Circular Arch Shapes under Multiple Load Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Arch shape is one of the oldest used in architecture and structural engineering, but thanks to its efficiency it is still frequently used, specially, for long span bridges. The shape of an arch is reached at the conceptual design stage, usually resulting in one of three idealized configurations: circular, parabolic or catenary. These forms become bending-less arches under certain fixed load conditions. Although the real structural elements are subjected to a huge number of possible load combinations, there is an only one “bending-less” configuration that is possible, while the safety evaluation must be conducted for each possible load configurations, that means considering static coupling effects of bending and shear actioning on each arch sections. In this paper is evaluated an optimal configuration of a circular arch, subjected to different vertical load combinations, evaluating the height to span ratio, the cross section (hypothesized constant along the arch) and the inertia modulus, as the main representative parameters to be considered. The analysis is performed with the aim to evaluate the optimal configuration able to minimize the self-weight of the arch, not only to limit the materials but also to find solutions for the constructive stages. The analysis is performed using a numerical solution of circular arches equations neglecting shear and axial deformations and considering a homogeneous material. The objective function considered is the total arch weight, while the load is applied in symmetrical and antisymmetrical configurations.

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Emergent Design for Complex structures based on High-Performance Fibre-Reinforced Cement Based Materials

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen was intentionally introduced into ultra-high strength steel by cadmium plating. The purpose was to examine the effect of cadmium plate thickness, and hence, hydrogen on the Charpy Impact strength of the steel. The AISI 4340 steel was austenitized at 1000 °C for 1 hour, water quenched, and tempered at temperatures between 494 and 1100 °C in order to achieve a range of targeted strength levels. The specimens were cadmium plated with 0.00508mm (0.2 mils), 0.00762mm (0.3 mils), and 0.0127mm (0.5 mils). Results demonstrated that the uncharged specimens exhibited higher impact energy values when compared to the plated specimens at all tempering temperatures. The results of this work are best explained by the “Dislocation Transport (Sweeping) of Hydrogen” model.

Keywords: 4340 Steel, Charpy Impact Test, Hydrogen Charging, Cadmium Plating

DL-Scale: Deep Learning for Model Upgrading in Topology Optimization

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ABSTRACT

Topology optimization is used for defining the optimal arrangement of material within a specific domain with respect to transferring specific loads to predetermined supports in the best possible way. Deep learning techniques have achieved significant results in computer vision [1], natural language processing [1], big- data management [2], etc. On the contrary, not much work can be found in utilizing deep learning methods in structural engineering. In the current work, DL-Scale, a methodology based on a combination of a deep learning method along with a topology optimization method is presented, aiming in minimizing topology optimization computational loads and improving the usability of structural topology optimization. One of the most established methods in topology optimization is the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) [3]. While the quality of results of SIMP is extremely high, it is also notable that it is a computationally heavy method, especially when dealing with fine discretized meshes. Deep Belief Networks (DBN) are probabilistic generative models which are formulated by sequentially connecting Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBM) [2]. DBNs have been successfully applied in a series of problems by taking advantage of their ability to detect higher order correlations in large databases.

In the current work a new methodology is proposed where a DBN is used along with SIMP in an iterative manner for vastly reducing the computational loads of fine-discretized meshes in topology optimization through model upgrading. This is achieved by training the DBN in finding hidden patterns and correlations between initial densities of finite elements produced by SIMP and the final density per element that SIMP proposes. The network is trained once on a typical topology optimization reference problem and is tested against several known to literature problems. For applying the methodology in a specific problem with dense meshing, a number of identical sub-problems are created with significantly less dense meshes and are handled sequentially. The generated sub-models are identical to the original one in terms of loading conditions, support conditions, etc. It is proven in all test cases examined and presented that the above-mentioned model-upgrading methodology manages to minimize the computational load of topology optimization as the iterations that SIMP needs to perform on a dense meshed model are vastly reduced.

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DzAIN: Deep Learning Based Generative Design

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ABSTRACT

Generative Design is the methodology for automatic creation of a large number of designs via an iterative algorithmic framework while respecting user-defined criteria and limitations. It is mainly used as a designer assistive tool for the creation of prototypes in sectors like product manufacturing, automotive and aerospace industry while there are also references of use of Generative Design in architecture [1]. The algorithms used are mainly originating from nature-mimicking procedures [2]. Generative Design differentiates from shape optimization due to the fact that it does not focus on finding the optimal design but on being able to propose a large variety of designs that satisfy all designer-defined constraints in an automated procedure. Thus, it can be said that it focuses on proposing initial designs for inspiring the designer.

In this work, a methodology for Generative Design called DzAIN is proposed. DzAIN is based on an algorithmic architecture that combines topology optimization and deep learning methods. Deep learning and specifically Deep Belief Networks (DBN) [3] are used for diversifying, through stochasticity, designs generated by topology optimization method Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) [4]. SIMP is used for guiding the design procedure towards a local optima. The response time for DzAIN to propose a series of shapes is minimal as only a small population of SIMP iterations is needed while the time needed for application of a series of DBNs is insignificant. In the current work, a series of examples of computer generated designs with the use of DzAIN are presented in order to validate the proposed methodology.

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Optimizing Stages of Restoration of Fujian Tulou through Participatory Design and Collective Practices

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ABSTRACT

Fujian Tulou is a significant part of the international built heritage. Renovation and strengthening of existing Haka Tulou's earth constructions contribute to a better quality of life improvement of those who stay at earth buildings and for an increase of long lasting levels of China's heritage.

Previous studies of Fujian Tulou mainly cover habitation patterns, construction features and architectural details. In this research a layout have been summarized of causes of deterioration, pathology of structure, focused on the buildings' conservation value and restoration, in terms of history, culture and construction technologies.

Out of Fujian's more than 3,000 tulou, only a few dozen have been awarded the status of World Heritage Sites by UNESCO. Along with that status, the 46 buildings chosen for the award. The buildings which

belong to Unesco's heritage are on list of possible restoration, but the rest must remain in disintegration while the same time villages are getting vacant through years.

The answer of the restoration could be found through participation and team work of experts and habitants. A Tulou is usually inhabited by one family clan of several generations, and the enclosed structure allows for members to work together and participate in common goal.

How can we form the ground for habitant's participation? In what extent could Tulou's studies contribute to rehabilitation practices of these buildings in a collaborative and participatory way? How can it be established collaboration between engineer-experts and local people for the Tulou's restoration? Finally it will be presented a methodological tool for the participatory restoration of an architectural heritage made of earth.

* The asterisk denotes the presenting author.

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Optimization of Public Spaces through Network Potentials of Communities

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ABSTRACT

Although public spaces may vary in great extent in morphology, use and typology it is of no doubt that they formulate a network of places offered to the citizens to use. Alongside community can be described as both people being in a similar geographical location as well as people having a particular interest or characteristic in common. Therefore communities also have the potential to form a strong network system supporting and effecting public spaces.

What is the role of local authorities to the sense of civic engagement and the sense of belonging of public spaces? How could local authority's practices enhance and support collective practices of maintenance and use? Practices such as participatory placemaking, co-designing, location based digital content and their impact will be mentioned and further analyzed.

In what extent could these practices optimize public places and lead communities' cohesion and an overall increase of citizens' and city's wellbeing? How vary practices may differentiate the use of public space, the sense of a place and the overall sense of a city enhancing the use and the maintenance of public spaces?

Showcases and potentials of the municipality of Chania will be examined highlighted and further analyzed.

* The asterisk denotes the presenting author.

Optimization Practice of Water Resources for the Needs of the Local Communities in mainland Greece (case study of Karies Peloponnese)

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ABSTRACT

Water is the basis of our civilization and the development of society is intertwined with the exploitation of water resources in various scales, from an agricultural drill used to irrigate a garden, to a large dam providing water and energy for a large area. However, for remote mountainous areas, intermittent natural water resources and high seasonal demand the above tasks become more challenging. This analysis presents various alternative management proposals and appropriate solutions on how to exploit water resources meeting the above restrictions under limited infrastructure budgets. As a case study we examine the area of Karies in Peloponnese that meets the above criteria, exploring various solutions to satisfy the water demand.

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Method for Designing Optimal Usable Structures of Computer System for its Emergency Reconfiguration

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ABSTRACT

The work deals with the reconfiguration of computer system, which was designed to provide services from a strictly defined set. We assume that the system is fully usable, as long as each randomly appearing request to perform any service from this set will be handled. When such a request occurs, the technical resources required for its fulfillment must be allocated to the service. In the general case, the same technical resources can be dedicated to perform various services at different moments of time. Therefore, it is advisable to introduce abstract resources, so-called functional ones, representing particular types of actual technical resources. Functional resources mediate in linking the services and technical resources required to perform them. One functional resource can be associated with only one service, whereas it can be performed by various technical resources.

Each set of pairs $\langle \text{service}, \text{functional resource} \rangle$, constituting a subset of the full set of such pairs, determined at the design stage of the system, creates the so-called the system's functional structure. In the case of damage of technical resource, it cannot be ruled out that it is impossible to maintain full usability of the system, i.e. to create an complete usable structure. However, as a rule, it will be possible to create more than one of its substructures, each of them provides support for service requests from a subset of the established set of services. If it is permissible to provide services to a limited extent for established subsets of services and for each of them a loss function resulting from the inability to provide a given service was specified, the system should be reconfigured (using available technical resources) so as to create a usable structure, at which potential losses will be the smallest..

The results of previous works are as follows:

- an algorithm for interactive fixing acceptable substructures by a user, reducing to the necessary minimum the number of required indications of service subsets (n services is 2^n possible subsets). Indeed, the choice comes down to establish vectors of minimal reliability functions. That algorithm has been implemented,
- a general algorithm for determining optimal functional substructures at a given state of fitness of the system. It can be the basis for the design of the layer for controlling automated system reconfiguration.

The presented approach allows to reduce losses in the case of a lack of full possibilities of supplying services by the system. The proposed method, after some extensions, can be applied to reconfigure non-computer systems, e.g. the state security system.

Topology Optimization of Framed Structures using SAP2000

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ABSTRACT

Over the recent years, topology optimization is increasingly used by engineers as a powerful free-form design tool, which aims to find the optimum material distribution within a design domain. It is extensively applied to various fields like aeronautics, automotive and aerospace by using the continuum mechanics approach. However, its application to civil engineering is limited. In the proposed paper, topology optimization is performed in structures with 1D members (truss and frames) by using SAP2000. SAP2000 is a well-known commercial software for analysis and design of structural systems that is equipped with an open application programming interface (OAPI). The optimization problem is solved using the High-Performance Optimization Computing Platform (HP-OCP). The problem formulation and the objective functions calculations are written in C#, while the optimization solver (PQN) in FORTRAN.

The topology optimization problem of structures that are composed by 1D finite elements is mainly divided in two stages. Firstly, the generation of the initial design domain, usually called as ground structures and secondly, the formulation of the optimization problem. Several articles that deal with the ground structure generation can be found in literature some of which also provide programming code, such as T. Zegard et al. [1]. However, most of them deal with 2D structures and have many limitations. In our work we used the Grasshoppers, a plugin of the CAD program Rhino, which is a wide-spread free form design tool that many architects use. An additional tool written in C# was developed, to transfer the initial geometry in SAP2000 and formulate the optimization problem. The proposed method is implemented both in 2D and 3D problems.

The second step is, the definition of the boundary conditions of the structure, the selection of the objective function, the constraints and the mathematic optimization algorithm. Changizi et al. [2] presents a stress-based topology optimization problem of frame structures with standard cross sections. In the proposed paper, the objective function of the optimization problem is the compliance and the constraints we used is the volume of the final structure and the design code regulations. Due to difficulties in numerical implementation, simple member cross-sectional geometries are used (circular and rectangle). However, with some modifications the problem can be extended to members with more complicated cross-section. This is a project we already working on and results are expected in an upcoming paper.

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High Performance Topology Optimization Computing Platform**Sotiropoulos Stefanos^{1*}, Nikos D. Lagaros²**¹National Technical University of Athensst.sotirop@gmail.com²National Technical University of Athensnlagaros@central.ntua.gr**ABSTRACT**

One of the most challenging tasks in the construction industry nowadays, is to reduce the material demands and distribute, in the same time, the material among the structural system in the best possible way. Topology optimization is a design procedure that is increasingly used, to generate optimized forms of structures in several engineering fields. The current paper presents the Topology Optimization (TO) module of the High-Performance Optimization Computing Platform (HP-OCP) which focuses on civil engineering problems.

More specifically the SIMP method [1] is implemented and the topology optimization problem is solved by using both OC and MMA algorithms. The HP-OCP is a platform which evaluates several objective functions, such as the volume of the structure, the compliance etc. and can solve constrained or unconstrained structural optimization problems. The above libraries are developed in C#. The core of the platform is created in such way that it can be integrated with any CAE program that has OAPI. In the proposed work we used the structural analysis and design software SAP2000.

Lagaros et al. [2] presented a C# code that solves topology optimization problems, which are discretized with 3D solid elements, using SAP2000. One of the highlights of the proposed work is that the above module can be used for all kind of finite elements. Benchmark tests are presented with structures that are simulated by 2D plane-stress elements, 3D-solid elements and shell elements. Furthermore, it is independent of the type of the mesh, structured or unstructured, so both examples are presented. In addition, a tool in C# was developed in order to connect Rhino's plugin Grasshoppers with SAP2000. In that way more complicated geometries can be generated in the CAD program Rhino then the structural engineering problem can be formulated in SAP2000 and finally the above module can solve the topology optimization problem.

In the proposed work a powerful tool for both architects and civil engineers is introduced. The capabilities of the TO module of the HP-OCP are presented and several test cases are shown. The analysis and design of the structures are performed in SAP2000 software, in order to achieve a realistic result that could be a solution for a real-world structure.

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Transformable Building Envelope Design in Architectural Education

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ABSTRACT

Transformable building envelope design plays a key role in energy performance and sustainability considering the thermal, lighting, acoustic, and visual occupants' comfort, as well as aesthetics, economics and durability. Kinetic building envelopes can provide a real-time process of reconfiguration enlivening the environmental performance compared to conventional static building envelopes and enhancing the end-users' internal comfort. Transformable systems may be further developed for direct application on building façades, in order to provide control of natural lighting, ventilation and temperature of the inner spaces through their own surface openings and materials. In architectural education, transformable building envelope design refers to an integrated approach of architectural development in terms of morphology, structure and construction. The methodology exposes students to the design logic of responsive systems as related with aspects of sustainability, materiality, functionality and aesthetics on one side and structure kinematics and stability on the other side. The pedagogical approach of the presented projects conducted focuses on a non-linear technological-driven analysis throughout different scales of development, from the element, to the system and building envelope scale. The primary aims of the projects involve the conceptualization, investigation and analysis of the developed kinetic mechanisms in physical models, geometrical simulations, motion analyses and daylight performance. Through physical and digital models, students are better prepared to gain insight to the transformable system behavior by means of motion and daylight performance. Further related optimization-driven analysis would enable the design of transformable building envelopes at element and system level.

Structural Optimization Computing Platform (SOCP) and SCIA Software

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ABSTRACT

Structural analysis programs usually compute a static model with cross sections given by the engineer or set to reasonable defaults. Any optimization of the structure with respect to a variable, for example weight/cost, is left to the experience of the engineer, usually because adding optimization capabilities to a structural analysis program is not trivial. Many optimization algorithms are available, each one with their own peculiarities, requirements, and performance. The variable to optimize is different for different projects such as material cost, construction cost, first eigen frequency and others. Adding to the complexity is the fact a static or dynamic analysis is computational expensive (time consuming) and thus the algorithms must be tuned to perform as few static analyses as possible.

Optimization Computing Platform (OCP) is software developed at ISAAR NTUA, which in combination

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with widely known structural analysis programs such as SAP2000 and ETABS, can optimize any structure with various algorithms, and with respect to various variables or a combination of them. Recently, OCP is actively developed to be program agnostic, so that it can be linked with any structural analysis program. The program gains painlessly mature and sophisticated optimization capabilities.

In this case study OCP platform was linked with SCIA engineering, structural analysis and design software to provide addition optimization capabilities. To validate the software connection a number of structural examples are tested with very good results.

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Two-Scale Topology Optimization using Homogenization Theory

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ABSTRACT

The two scale topology optimization formulation is a mathematical procedure which focuses on finding the optimal layout of a structure, by changing the topological characteristics of the many different unit cells consisting it. These unit cells are most commonly referred to as the “the micro scale” part of the optimization problem and the structure as the “the macro scale” part. The optimization procedure used to define the topology of the unit cells is the topology optimization formulation, modified to combine the information deriving from the two different scales involved. In addition with topology optimization, the most common theory used for connecting the properties of the two separate scales is the theory of homogenization. By applying the homogenization theory in each optimization loop the different topologies of the micro scale produce elasticity tensors which are consequently used as material parameters for the elements consisting the macro scale.

The main focus of the study is the comparison of different formulations for performing the two scale optimization procedure as well as the efficiency of the different topology optimization approaches and different solvers. In addition a 3D case study will be presented demonstrating the capabilities of the two scale topology optimization in more complex problems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Control of Vibrations of Common Pedestrian Bridges in Jordan with Tuned Mass Dampers

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ABSTRACT

Pedestrian bridges are sensitive to human induced vibrations and thus vibration-serviceability assessment becomes a crucial issue in the design process. Excessive vibrations cause discomfort and in some cases cause resonance and catastrophic failure with priceless human and economical losses. This study evaluates the response of typical pedestrian bridges built in Jordan under human-induced vibrations; especially those with fundamental frequencies between 2 to 4 Hz. Footbridges with such low fundamental frequencies can be excited by human movement (walking, jumping or running), which leads to synchronizing and resonance conditions. The concept of integration Tuned Mass Dampers (TMD) within the structure of a footbridge to minimize the human-induced vibrations (displacement, velocity and acceleration) is a major goal of this study. A common simply supported steel footbridge in Jordan located on Irbid- Amman Highway is simulated using ETABS version 17 software to identify its dynamic properties including frequency, natural period, stiffness and mode shapes. Then the critical span length that leads to excessive lateral and vertical vibrations is identified. The footbridge is excited with walking and running loading scenarios by applying time-history analysis. The response of the footbridge is compared with and without special TMD tuned with the fundamental frequency of the footbridge in order to optimize its mass, stiffness and damping coefficient. It was observed that after attaching the TMD, the fundamental vibration frequency decreased to stable value less than human excitation frequencies. Also, acceleration, velocity, and displacement were decreased significantly falling within acceptable limits. Recommendations and guidelines were given for designing common footbridges in Jordan.

Enhancement of the Mechanical Properties of Kaolin Geopolymer Using Sodium Hydroxide and Calcium Oxide

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the effect of adding sodium hydroxide and calcium oxide on the mechanical properties of kaolin-based geopolymer binder. Geopolymer binder was first prepared using calcined kaolin as aluminosilicate precursor and sodium silicate as alkaline activator. The calcium and sodium hydroxide were then added at dosages of 0, 5, 10, 15, and 20% by weight of kaolin, and the compressive strength was measured for specimens cured at room and elevated temperature. The results showed that the addition of either 5 wt.% sodium hydroxide, or 10 wt.% calcium oxide dramatically increased the room-temperature compressive strength of kaolin geopolymer by 90% and 105%, respectively. Addition of either 5 wt.% sodium hydroxide, or 10 wt.% calcium oxide has also improved the water stability of the kaolin geopolymer by about 120%. X-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) test techniques were performed to get insight the binder microstructural phases and its chemical characteristics.

Keywords: Kaolin, Geopolymer, water stability, compressive strength

Typology-Based Generation of Multi-Family-Residential Buildings

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ABSTRACT

The design process in architecture can be characterized as a multi-criteria optimization problem to find a solution or a set of solutions offering the best possible trade-offs between the social, ecological, and economic performance of the buildings. The main difficulty faced by the architects while searching for the optimal solution is a) a large number of design options and b) to identify the essential design criteria to evaluate. If the former characterizes the size of the design space and the latter its dimensions, there exists an almost infinitely large, multidimensional space full of possible building designs. As a consequence, it is usually not possible to search through the whole design space to guarantee that the “true” optimal solution is found. Instead, the process of design resembles a systematic search where every new design variant found in the design space brings the designer eventually closer to the optimum. Therefore, the goal of this research is to develop a method of an efficient automatized search through the vast solution space, avoiding to waste time on nonsensical variants. This method is utilized to design residential buildings layouts.

Our approach applies common strategies traditionally applied in the field of architecture. By using typologies, we restrict the infinite size of the design space to a smaller finite set of well-established solutions. This strategy guides the search process by past experiences and insights (e.g., well performing existing solutions) and therefore, the chances for improving the existing solution increase. We present a generative tool that automatically tests different typologies and their variations on a particular site, defined by the user. To produce practically applicable results, the surrounding building context and the locally applied building regulations are considered during the generation process. For example, we consider necessary spacings to the sides of the plot, dependent on the position of the neighboring buildings. Additionally, the tool provides an interface for the user to interact with the generation process by defining and limiting different parameters. By modifying input parameter boundaries like for building height or depth, the users can influence the various heuristic strategies of the generation. To identify the best options among the generated ones, we implement different analysis modules such as construction cost estimates, various area calculations, and daylight simulations. Since every specific design problem has different criteria to judge the performance of the design, the approach is implemented in a modular

way allowing to extend the existing analysis to provide the necessary flexibility during the evaluation process.

To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed approach, we test the generated candidates in several real-world scenarios and compare them against the traditionally developed and built solutions. As evaluation criteria, we consider the performance of the design as well as the resources required to find it expressed in terms of time. As a result, we can quantify the direct benefits of combining traditional design methods with the power of generative computational algorithms on the design of residential buildings.

Semi-Analytical Solution of in-Plane Vibrations of Circular Arches

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ABSTRACT

In spite of the wide use in modern civil engineering of straight structural components made of reinforced concrete, such as beams and slabs, arches still remain quite often adopted in architectural design, due to their interesting mechanical and esthetical properties. Therefore, practical analytical and numerical tools should be available in order to allow designers to ensure the resistance and stability of this type of structures, especially in the dynamic regime and when point masses are added. The sixth degree differential equation of motion of inextensible arches is known to be quite difficult to deal with and is not applicable to the case examined here of arches with added point masses [1]. The procedure adopted in this article consisted on finding relatively easy particular solutions of this equation satisfying the end conditions and using them as trial functions in Rayleigh-Ritz formulations of the practical cases of interest. Circular arches of different opening angles are examined here under the classical hypotheses: (1) the effect of shear deformation and rotary inertia are neglected (2) the arch axis is inextensible (3) the dimensions of the cross-section are small in comparisons with the radius, (4) the cross-section is uniform. Three different kinds of end conditions are considered: simply supported-simply supported (SS), clamped-simply supported (CS) and clamped-clamped (CC). The Rayleigh-Ritz method allowed in each case to determine, via an algebraic solution of the associated eigenvalue problem, the first seven mode shapes and natural frequencies of arches with different values of the opening angle. The comparison with the results available in the bibliography was satisfactory and the mode shapes were plotted. The second part of this work was devoted to arches with added concentrated masses: likewise, the numerical values found for the natural frequencies compare quite well with the few references available and the mode shapes are plotted showing the effects of the opening angle, the mass and the positions of the added point masses.

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Carbon Nanotubes Dosage Optimization for Strength Enhancement of Cementitious Composites

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ABSTRACT

Concrete is the most common used material for construction in Qatar as well as in the world. Exposure to sever environmental conditions causes physical deterioration of concrete structures and significantly affect the concrete's strengths and modulus of elasticity. In the last decades, many improvements had been made in concrete technology. Most of these improvements focused at macro and micro level to improve the behavior of concrete. However, better enhancement in the performance of cementitious materials could be achieved at nano level where the cracks start to initiate. The development of reinforcing materials at the nanoscale has opened a new field of research within concrete technology. Nanomaterials were recently entitled to be a promising substitute to the traditional supplementary cementitious materials in order to improve the mechanical properties and the durability of cement-based materials due to its outstanding mechanical and thermal properties and unique geometrical characteristics. This research focuses on carbon nanotubes dosage optimization for strength enhancement of cementitious composites. Four dosages of carbon nanotubes; 0%, 0.05%, 0.1%, and 0.2% by weight of cement) were added into cement mortar to explore the optimum dosage that can lead to big enhancement in mechanical strengths of cementitious composites. The mechanical strengths were investigated in terms of compressive and flexural strengths. The results revealed that adding small amount of carbon nanotubes could enhance the compressive strength of cement mortar but not the flexural strength.

Parametric Analyses for the Evaluation of Soil-Structure Interaction Effects on Eigenfrequencies and Damping Ratios

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ABSTRACT

The present paper evaluates the effects of soil-structure interaction on the eigenfrequency and damping ratio related to the translational degree of freedom of the superstructure of a 3DOF system. The degrees of freedom correspond to: i) translation of superstructure; ii) translation of foundation and iii) rotation of foundation. The discrete analytical model exploits frequency dependent impedance functions of a foundation supported at the surface of a nondissipative, homogeneous, linearly elastic halfspace.

The interacting system does not possess classical normal modes and a standard modal analysis is not rigorously applicable. Therefore, numerical free vibration experiments are performed applying a code written in MATLAB, in order to estimate modal characteristics.

Parametric analyses are conducted with changes in wave parameter, taking into account the variation of the following measures: i) Poisson's ratio of soil; ii) slenderness ratio of superstructure and iii) mass ratio of superstructure and foundation. Results indicate that soil-structure interaction effects decrease the eigenfrequency but may either reduce or increase the damping ratio. In the small value range of the wave parameter there is an increase of the damping ratio; in the medium value range a decrease may be detected while in the high value range, usually is equal to the structural damping. The decrease of Poisson's ratio leads to a more flexible system but with smaller damping ratio. Finally, the increase of foundation inertia increases the damping ratio, especially for small values of the wave parameter.

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For each of these objective functions, candidate designs are to be assessed for embodied energy ^[10] to determine individual relationships. It is anticipated that correlation can be derived, and collective relationships between design and state variables and embodied energy can be determined.

To the authors best knowledge, such an approach has not been previously undertaken to determine relationships between design and state variables to embodied energy for a single beam. This initial study is

an important starting point prior to assessing more complex structures, and determining structural form as a function of embodied energy.

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Computer-Aided Approach to Public Buildings Floor Plan Generation Generator

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ABSTRACT

For architects as well as developers and urban planners working on the floor plans or estimating the shape and dimensions of large buildings is always a challenge. This task requires some knowledge and what is more important – even with understanding of the process it is a very time-consuming task. One should take into consideration the arrangement of all rooms as well as adjacencies and connections of main spaces

Presented project can be considered as an exploration of various ways of generating floor plans for public buildings, which was followed by creating a new algorithm for solving that task. Public buildings were chosen as a main target of conducted research because of their complex and non-standardized structure. The aim was to try different previously described approaches, invent completely new techniques and methods, choose the best of them and incorporate them into my own algorithm.

The statement was put on as a starting point: Each of the rooms in a building is somehow accessible from any other room. It means that the whole communication structure is interlinked and thus forms the core. It could be said that the first step of the generation would be developing an evacuation plan, which can later be converted into more intelligible communication network.

Floor plans analysis was conducted in order to understand the structural patterns of communication spaces in built public houses. One of positive outcomes of this investigation is that public buildings do not share a lot of features in common, therefore this field of exploration is rather unobstructed and provides a lot of possibilities for experiments.

Ease of use was considered as a crucial feature since the beginning of a project. Therefore, a simple solution for managing a room program of a house was created for the Grasshopper environment. It enables user to set basic parameters, such as room name, area, room connections, entrance location, type of space (room/hall).

The outcomes of current development phase have already proved the applicability of the chosen approach, although a lot of work is still required. The research and the generator development led to some undisclosed subjects to emerge, for example: how strong the connection between the topological building floor plan and its geometrical plan is? Is the set of connection structure, room areas and boundary enough for generating relatively viable plan? How one can overcome the restrictions set by square grid? Can an algorithm generate a better communication structure than human can? All these questions are highly relevant to the research and thus need to be answered, or at least investigated.

Evaluation of Optimal Lateral Resisting Systems for Tall Buildings Subject to Horizontal Loads

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ABSTRACT

The tendency of modern designs towards optimal structures often leads to the lightest and best performing choice among a large set of design alternatives. In a similar scenario, the introduction of automated tools to further guide designers in achieving efficient solutions has been a recurrent topic for mechanical and structural engineers, over the past decades. Nowadays, topology optimization is considered a powerful preliminary design tool to determine the optimal material distribution in a design domain, i.e. the most effective configuration that satisfies a given set of prescribed constraints while reducing the consumption of structural material. Among different applications in the field of Civil Engineering, this work focuses on the definition of optimal layouts of lateral resisting systems for multi-storey steel building frameworks subject to lateral loads using topology optimization techniques. The objective of the research is to illustrate the benefits deriving from the introduction of automated routines within the preliminary design stage and establish reliable guidelines for performing accurate and objective optimization procedures. Since the optimal material distribution follows the load flow within the structure, optimal topologies are especially sensitive to the alteration of support and loading conditions: different loading scenarios naturally lead to distinct optimal layouts. In order to avoid the loss of objectivity and preserve the optimality of the results, the effects that preliminary modelling and loading assumptions produce on final layouts are investigated. Numerical applications to high-rise building models, with different aspect ratios and loading conditions, are presented and discussed. The problem is settled using a minimum compliance formulation to compare the material distribution results with those examined in the literature. Two-dimensional case studies are analysed via the topology optimization of a planar lateral resisting

system, envisioned as part of a 3D building. The 2D representation, in fact, allows handling and dominating the basic issues generally arising in more realistic models, without adding further complexity to the problem.

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Integrating Model Simulations and Smart Sensing for the Coupled Transport-Degradation Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Structures

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ABSTRACT

The new advances in sensor and information technologies and the wide use of the Internet make structural health monitoring (SHM) a promising technology for better management of civil engineering structures. Transport-related degradation of concrete materials is a major factor in the premature deterioration of concrete structures. The huge costs of maintaining or replacing deteriorated structures, the implications of this on the environment and society, and the impetus to increase the sustainability of the constructed environments have created an urgent need for the development of the model-based simulation of the durability of reinforced concrete structures. The primary objective of this paper is to develop a model-based simulation for the transport-degradation behavior and then validating these simulations by experimental measurements using smart sensing technologies. A finite element software package will be identified, and then used to simulate the transport processes. The simulation will be then verified by experimental investigations using smart sensor technologies.

Keywords: Structural health monitoring, model-based simulations, smart sensing

Optimization Based Feasibility Study for Filler Slabs as A Response Towards the ECBC Roof Compliance with Respect to Thermal Transmittance

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ABSTRACT

The Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) is being made mandatory in India. The architects should ensure that the buildings they design must comply with the criteria for energy efficiency. This research talks about filler slabs as a possible solution for roofing in buildings. One component of ECBC is the thermal transmittance of roof as per section 4, clause 4.3.1. Optimum selection of materials for fillers will reduce the heat transfer, which further leads to the reduction in energy consumption.

A framework has been developed that allows architects to select the optimum combination of the materials based on different parameters, at different stages, that is u value, pricing and availability, for different commercial building typologies in different climatic zones of India. This research is subjected to the availability of the filler materials that have been tested for their thermal conductivity (k value) in the Indian context. The list of materials formulates the range for selected variables, which has been used for the optimization in the mathematical model.

This mathematical model generates the result for six building typologies, five climatic zones, three levels of ECBC, two grades of steel and concrete used and six slab thickness. There has been total of 2160 cases that arise by permutation and combination. This optimization produces the optimum choice for filler material in every case based upon the variables and associated constraints. In those cases where the solution cannot be derived, it is deduced that filler slabs is not feasible to be used as a solution for the ECBC compliance.

Keywords: optimization, energy conservation, u value, filler material, feasibility.

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Optimization based Feasibility Analysis for Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) Compliance of Opaque Wall Assemblies in Different Climatic Zones of India

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid development of modern society, energy consumption is a major concern all over the world. Building energy consumption takes a large proportion in the total energy consumption, and thus attracts much attention. Thermal performance of building envelopes is the determinant factor of building energy consumption.

Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) for commercial buildings was first launched in 2007 as a voluntary code towards establishing new benchmarks for energy efficient buildings in India. There has been inadequate implementation of ECBC in the country and adoption of these codes has not been swifter. The success of these codes, policies and regulations depends on the market response to be self-sustaining in the long term.

This research uses the evolutionary optimization model for the feasibility analysis of ECBC and incremental ECBC 2017 code compliance, in various climatic zones of India towards wider acceptability by the building industry with respect to the thermal transmittance of opaque wall assemblies in building envelope for different typologies of commercial buildings using the available materials in the Indian context / market. This study classifies all of the materials available in the market for wall construction in three parts with respect to inside finishing, main wall/block material and outside finishing, to explore all of the possibilities for various types of wall in different contexts and constraints such as thickness, finishing of the wall (exposed, etc.), climate, etc.

This analysis will help the policy designers to understand the implementation level issues with respect to the materials available in the market.

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Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) based optimum wall with respect to Thermal transmittance and thickness composition for different commercial pockets of tier 1 city in temperate climatic zone of India

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, there is a surge in the commercial sector in the tier 1 cities of India. Due to the demand for an increase in the commercial spaces, there is a scope for increased investments in these sectors. The study presented in this paper tries to focus on maximizing the selling price of properties in commercial sectors by suggesting the thinnest possible optimized external wall that eventually results in increased carpet area in a building. The wall combinations to be optimized will be compliant to the Energy Conservation Building Code 2017 of India (ECBC, 2017) with respect to the thermal transmittance (u-value). To achieve the same, geographic information system-based study of tier 1 city, from the temperate climatic zone of India, given by the ECBC 2017, has been studied to find the various commercial pockets in the city. According to Central Pay Commission, Government of India, the ranking system for the classification of Indian cities is based on the House Rent Allowance (HRA), which classifies cities into three classes, Tier-1, Tier-2, and Tier-3 cities.

Three material library of different materials, which can be used for the inside finishing of the wall, main block/brick element of the walls and exterior finishing of the wall, has been taken into consideration based upon availability in the country. The various wall compositions achieved, as the result of an evolutionary optimization is made compliant with the ECBC 2017 standards to obtain the best possible optimized external wall solution. The increase in the percentage of carpet area/ sellable area as a result of optimization of the external wall was used to calculate the percentage increase in the profit per square meter area of construction. As a final result of the optimization, the selling price of the commercial building is maximized.

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The Effectiveness of Intersections Controlled by Roundabouts and Traffic Signals: An Assessment Study Around Yarmouk University

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ABSTRACT

The significant increase in traffic and the limited capacity of traffic roadways and intersections force traffic engineers to think of a new way in which to control vehicles. This paper presents current practices concerning the design and operation of roundabouts and traffic signals and investigates which control mechanism is better on both intersection and network (regional) levels.

The network around Yarmouk University (YU) in Irbid, Jordan was chosen to be the test location as one of the busiest zones in the city of Irbid. Four significant intersections around YU is within the scope of this project. Several types of data were collected to be used in this study covering the geometric part (number of lanes, lane width, etc.), traffic volume (peak hour volume at intersections, heavy vehicle %, etc.), traffic control (stop signs, yield signs, speed limits, signal timing, etc.), and other operational data such as the average lane speed and delay. Through this research, traffic software has been used, such as; SIDRA, TSIS-CORSIM, and HCS. The analysis was performed on both the intersection and network level. Model development was built based on the existing geometric, traffic, and control conditions. Calibration and validation results showed acceptable statistics with R^2 equal to 0.86 for speed results, and 0.78 for traffic turning movements. Three alternatives were formulated and analyzed to reduce traffic congestion in the study area: Scenario 1 (S1) the existing condition, Scenario 2 (S2) all intersections controlled by roundabouts, and Scenario 3 (S3) all intersections controlled by traffic signals.

Keywords: Roundabout, Traffic Signal, Simulation, Level of Service, LOS, Traffic Volume, Speed, Delay.

Dome Space Frames Optimization Using three Meta-Heuristic Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Domes are architectural and elegant structures that cover a vast area with no interrupting columns in the middle using suitable shapes and can also be economical. Domes are built in a wide variety of forms and specialized terms are available to describe them. According to their form, domes are given special names such as network, lamella, Schwedler, ribbed, and geodesic domes.

In this research, an optimum design algorithm is performed, using particle swarm optimization (PSO), colliding body optimization (CBO), and enhanced colliding bodies optimization (ECBO) method, to demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of the meta-heuristic method in creating optimal design for domes.

The network, lamella, ribbed, and Schwedler domes are studied to determine the optimum number of rings and the optimum height of crown and tubular sections of these domes. The minimum weight of each dome is taken as the objective function in the optimization process. A simple procedure is defined to determine the dome structures' configurations. This procedure includes calculating the joint coordinates and element connectivity. The design constraints are implemented according to the provision of LRFD - AISC (Load and Resistance Factor Design - American Institute of Steel Constitution).

A simple procedure is defined to determine the configurations of Schwedler and ribbed domes. This procedure includes calculation of the joint coordinates and element constructions. Nonlinear analysis is performed, due to the imperfections arising either from the manufacturing process and/or from the construction of the structure.

A comparative study for domes using different algorithms is carried out. The optimal design of different topology of domes is investigated with the effect of the number of joints in each ring and joint coordinate to verify the suitability of design procedure and to demonstrate effectiveness of the meta-heuristic algorithms.

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A Review on Optimal Design of Large-scale Suspended-dome using Meta Heuristic Method

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ABSTRACT

The suspended dome system is a new structural form that has become popular in the construction of long-span roof structures. Suspended dome is a kind of new prestressed space grid structure that has complex mechanical characteristics. In this study, an algorithm is developed for optimum design of domes considering the topology, geometry, and size of member section using the cascade-enhanced colliding bodies optimization method. In large-scale space steel structures, a large number of design variables are involved. The idea of cascade optimization allows a single optimization problem to be tackled in a number of successive autonomous optimization stages. The variables include the optimum height of crown and tubular sections of these domes, the initial strain, the length of the struts, and the cross-sectional areas of the cables in the tensegrity system of domes. The number of joints in each ring and the number of rings are considered for topology optimization of ribbed and Schwedler domes. The weight of the dome is taken as the objective function for minimization. A simple procedure is defined to determine the configuration of the domes. The design constraints are considered according to the provisions of Load and Resistance Factor Design—American Institute of Steel Construction.

In order to investigate the efficiency of the presented method, a large-scale suspended-dome with more than 2266 members is investigated. Large-scale steel space structure optimization with design code constraints is a difficult and complex problem. The performance of multi-DVC cascade and non-cascade methods is compared in the large-scale suspended-dome. The result shows that the multi-DVC cascade procedure reaches better design. In addition, the required number of analyses to achieve the best design

by the proposed method is lower. Number of analysis is important due to the high computational cost of the structural analysis in large-scale structures.

In this study, a suspended dome, with pin-joint single-layer reticulated shell and a suspended dome with rigid-joint single-layer reticulated shell, is discussed. A comparison is performed on efficiency of pin-joint, rigid-joint, and double layer domes. Also, a topology and geometry optimization for two common single layer domes are performed to find their optimum graphs considering various spans.

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Microstructure, Strength and Durability of Concrete Containing Volcanic Tuff as Supplementary Cementitious Material

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ABSTRACT

Currently, using cement in the concrete has negative effects. The reason is that cement consumes a large amount of energy during production. In addition, producing cement results in a large amount of CO₂ emissions. Accordingly, it was necessary to search for another material as a supplementary to cement. This supplementary material should be available and inexpensive. This research discusses the effect of substituting cement by volcanic tuff on workability, mechanical properties and durability of concrete. Five mixtures were carried out, one of these mixtures was control mix. Besides, the other four mixtures were carried out using different proportions between volcanic tuff and cement. These ratios were 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%. First, volcanic tuff was subjected to examination tests which evaluated chemical composition using X-Ray fluorescence (XRF). Then, slump, compressive strength, flexural strength, splitting tensile strength, pulse velocity, heat resistance, and absorption tests were performed on

concrete. Scanning electron microscopes (SEM) was applied for all specimens after 28 days while absorption test was applied after 28, 60, and 90 days. Decrease of slump values by increasing the percentage of replacement was observed. In all mixtures, the compressive strength decreased by increasing the percentage of cement replacement. Moreover, the maximum compressive strength was obtained for control mix (0% cement replacement). In addition, maximum tensile strength (flexure and splitting tensile test) were obtained for control mix and slightly decreased by increasing the percentage of replacement. Finally, when increasing the percentage of cement replacement, absorption of hardened concrete were increased and pulse velocity values were decreased.

Optimal Design Criteria for Seismic Retrofitting of RC Columns with Steel Jacketing Technique

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ABSTRACT

There are a wide number of existing building designed using codes that didn't considered at all or only limited seismic actions, while nowadays the actual codes takes care properly of this actions. As they are vulnerable to seismic events it is a key problems especially in those areas where the real seismic expositions has been upgraded in recent years. To reduce their vulnerability a common, cheaper and usually effective technique strategy for reinforced concrete buildings is the so called „Steel jacketing” (SJ) of columns, as it provide additional deformation and strength capacity to existing reinforced concrete (RC) frame structures. The use of SJ is associated with non-negligible costs depending on the amount of structural and non-structural manufacturing and materials. Moreover it is not easy to define how and which columns must be “upgraded” using this strategy. This research presents an optimization framework aimed at obtaining the optimal increase of seismic capacity/demand performance with minimization of retrofitting costs. It is shown the case study of a 3D RC frame implemented in OpenSEES and handled within the framework of a genetic algorithm. The algorithm iterates geometric and mechanical parameters configuration in order to match the optimal retrofitting solution based on static pushover analysis outcomes. Results of the proposed framework will provide optimized location and amount of steel-jacketing reinforcement, showing that the use of engineering optimization techniques can be effectively used to reduce retrofitting costs substantially unaltering structural safety.

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On the Performance of Differential Evolution Variants in Constrained Structural Optimization

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ABSTRACT

Constrained optimization is a highly important field of engineering as most real-world optimization problems are associated with one or several constraints. Such problems are often challenging to solve due to their complexity and high nonlinearity. Differential evolution (DE) is arguably one of the most versatile and stable population based search algorithm that exhibits robustness to multi-modal problems and has shown to be very efficient when solving constrained global optimization problems. In this paper we investigate the performance of several DE variants existing in the literature such as the traditional DE, the composite DE (CoDE) [1], the adaptive DE with optional external archive (JADE) [2] and the self-adaptive DE (jDE [3] and SaDE [4]), for handling constrained structural optimization problems. The performance of each DE variant is quantified by using four well-known benchmark structures in 2D and 3D. Various metrics are implemented, in an effort to create a fairly common assessment framework. It is shown that JADE, which updates control parameters in an adaptive way, truly exhibits superior performance and outperforms the other DE variants in all the cases examined.

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Optimal Design Criteria for Form Finding of Double Curved Surfaces

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ABSTRACT

In the last years, research on the design and construction of freeform architecture has significantly increased, due to the development of new digital design and fabrication technologies. In this framework, the proposed study focuses on form finding of concrete double curved surfaces.

At the aim to optimize every kind of shell surfaces, suitable form finding optimization methods are firstly investigated [1], focusing on the surface Stress Density method [2]. It allows to obtain an optimized shape by few parameters: the geometric characteristics of the start model, the surface density factor q_s , and the values of loads. By restricting the study on the single panel of the whole surface, a structural analysis is then carried out by SAP2000 software, in order to validate the resultant model and demonstrate that it is a shape resistant structure.

Finally a new production process for concrete double curved surfaces is investigated, answering to the needs of new shapes within architectural design [3]. The proposed solution is the improvement of an existing flexible mould formwork technology and represents a first attempt to reach a reusable, reconfigurable and affordable procedure.

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Optimizing the Impact of Detergents Contamination on the Geotechnical Properties of Soils

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of disposing commonly used detergents, namely Sodium Hypo-Chlorite, with a commercial name (Clorox), and Quaternary Ammonium Chloride commercially, known as (Flash), to soil on some of the geotechnical properties of different soils selected from three different locations in the northern part of Jordan. In order to achieve the goal of this research, two cohesive soils (Soil I and II) were selected. The initial physical properties of the selected soils including optimum moisture content, maximum dry density, grain size distribution, and cohesive soils unconfined compression tests were determined. A number of samples were prepared by mixing the soil with different percentages of detergents (Clorox and Flash) and their effects were studied by conducting different experiments such as the modified proctor compaction test, the unconfined test and Atterberg limits test. The results indicated that as the percentage of detergents increased, the plasticity index is slightly increased but the maximum dry density, water content and shear strength of cohesive soils (Soil-I and Soil-II) were decreased.

Key words: Detergents; Clayey soil; additives; Quaternary Ammonium Chloride; Sodium Hypo-Chlorite.

Assessment of the Impact of Potential Climate Change on the Surface Water of a Trans-Boundary Basin: Case Study Yarmouk River

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the long-term hydrological response (surface water) of a semi-arid trans-boundary basin to climate changes was analyzed. The basin is the Yarmouk River. The basin is located in a semi-arid region between Jordan and Syria. Concerns regarding the sensitivity of the Yarmouk River Basin (YRB) to potential climate change have prompted the authors to carry out the current study. The methodology adopted is based on simulating the hydrological response of the basin under statistically downscaled climate change scenarios. For this goal, the physically process-based semi-distributed hydrological model Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) has been used. The basin was modeled at two conditions: (1) The basin as if it has stayed without any manmade changes (pre-development), and (2) The basin as it gets changed in the life (post-development). The modeling evaluation measures indicated a satisfactory performance at the monthly scale under both conditions. The impact of climate change on YRB flow regime and water cycle components under pre-development and post-development conditions was evaluated by driving a satisfactorily calibrated SWAT model under the projected 21st-century climate change scenarios. The scenarios applied were the SRES A1B and A2 and CMIP5 RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios that had been downscaled from the CGCM3 and CanESM2 climate variables output, respectively. These scenarios were used as a basis for observing causal relationships among runoff, air temperature, and precipitation.

The results showed that the YRB surface water is very vulnerable and the major impact will be the spread of drought conditions without certain knowledge how severe it could be. Under the pre-development conditions, the impacts are believed to be some how disproportionate and of high risk. Under the post-development conditions, the impacts were of much less risk and proved the water

harvesting is an efficient way for adaptation. The applied changes of temperature from +0.9 to +3.7 C° and of precipitation from +6% to -32% during the 21st century may lead to Yarmouk river reduction - 2.6%-60% under the pre-development conditions and -0% to -36.4% under post-development conditions. This may be attributed to the inadequate downscaling ability to reproduce the actual precipitation pattern.. Such evaluation can help in enhancing the basin management, sustainable planning and building the adaptation schemes

Key words: SWAT, Climate change, statistical downscaling, surface water, hydrological modeling, trans-boundary basin, Jordan, Syria.

Rainfall-Runoff Modeling for Semi-arid and Trans-Boundary Yarmouk River Basin

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ABSTRACT

The capability of the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) to simulate streamflow for Yarmouk River Basin (YRB) is investigated. The YRB is a semi-arid and trans-boundary basin extends within two countries Jordan and Syria. The available daily precipitation, potential evapotranspiration and runoff data were used in conjunction with an optimization technique to calibrate SWAT a semi-distributed hydrological model. The basin was modeled at two conditions: (1) The basin as if it has stayed without any man made changes (pre-development) and (2) The basin as it gets changed in the life (post-development). The modeling evaluation measures indicated a satisfactory performance at the monthly scale under both conditions. For the pre-development condition, the model performed well for the YRB for which the coefficients of determination (R^2) were 0.87 and 0.81 both calibration (1986-1995) and validation (1996-2000) periods, respectively. The average monthly runoff from the model compared well to the observed average runoff. The error of the observed and simulated streamflow is within acceptance limit. Similarly, the model performed well for post-development conditions with R^2 of 0.89 and 0.81 for calibration and validation periods, respectively. The modeling results obtained in this study can be used by water authorities to enhance the water resources management of YRB. Moreover these results can be used to investigate the impact of climate change on the surface water resources of this basin.

Key words: SWAT, Yarmouk River, hydrological modeling, trans-boundary basin, Jordan, Syria.

Water Resources Management in Amman/Zarqa Basin (Al-Corridor Well Field)

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ABSTRACT

Al-Corridor (Well Field) locates to the north – east of Amman. According to Palestine Grid it lies between 285-305 E longitude and 165-185 N latitude. This well field had been subjected to exploitation of groundwater from new eleven wells since the 1999 with a total discharge of 11 MCM in addition to the previous discharge rate from the well field 14.7 MCM. Consequently, the aquifer balance is disturbed and a major decline in water level. Therefore, groundwater resources management is required to overcome the problems of water table decline and its effect on groundwater quality. Processing Modflow (PMWIN PRO, 2003) had been used in order to calculate the groundwater balance, aquifer properties, and to predict the aquifer response under different scenarios for the next 20 years (2035). The model was

calibrated for steady state conditions by trial and error calibration. The calibration was performed by matching observed and calculated initial heads for year 2001. Drawdown data for period 2001-2010 were used to calibrate transient model by matching calculated with observed one, after that, the transient model was validated by using the drawdown data for the period 2011-2014. The hydraulic conductivities of the Basalt- A7/B2 aquifer System are ranging between 1.0 and 8.0 m/day. The low conductivity value was found at the north-west and south-western parts of the study area, the high conductivity value was found at north-western corner of the study area and the average storage coefficient is about 0.025. The water balance for the Basalt and B2/A7 formation at steady state condition with a discrepancy of 0.003%. The major inflows come from Jabal Al Arab through the basalt and through the limestone aquifer (B2/A7 12.28 MCMY aquifer and from excess rainfall is about 0.68 MCM/a. While the major outflows from the Basalt-B2/A7 aquifer system are toward Azraq basin with about 5.03 MCMY and leakage to A1/6 aquitard with 7.89 MCMY. Four scenarios have been performed to predict aquifer system responses under different conditions. Scenario no.2 was found to be the best one which indicates that the reduction the abstraction rates by 50% of current withdrawal rate (25.08 MCMY) to 12.54 MCMY. The maximum drawdowns were decreased to reach about, 7.67 and 8.38m I n the years 2025 and 2035 respectively.

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Towards Effective BIM Adoption and Digital Transformation; Potential, Challenges and the Way Forward

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ABSTRACT

In this presentation the audience shall explore the unique experience of CCC, one of the Mega International Contractors, in the fields of BIM, digital transformation and asset lifecycle information management. True benefits for the effective utilization of BIM in construction of Buildings and Infrastructures shall be shared and revealed to the attendees followed by explaining the fundamental significance of proper BIM education, through CCC's BIM Academy contribution, for creating competent engineers and resources who can elevate organizations, clients, governments and societies awareness and readiness for digital transformation.

Linear Programming in the Analysis and Design of Structures

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ABSTRACT

The role of Linear Programming in design in general and limit analysis of structures in particular is addressed. Moreover, a procedure to determine the collapse load for three dimensional masonry structures using a standard limit analysis approach is presented [1], [2], [6]. The model consists of an assembly of three-dimensional macro-elements connected through plane interfaces. The degrees of freedom are considered at the centroids of the macro-elements and the internal forces on the plane interfaces. To formulate the governing equations following the displacement method, an equivalent frame assembly is considered, with the “nodes” corresponding to the macro-elements, considered at the centroids and the “members” corresponding to the interfaces.

Assuming Coulomb friction at the interfaces, several possible failure modes may govern the collapse mechanisms between two blocks. The ultimate limit states may involve, pure shear failure with relative displacements tangential to the interfaces, pure bending moment failure and pure torsional failure about the centroid of the interfaces. In addition, interaction effects are considered, such as those of combined torsion, shear and bending moments, which can be taken into account using a proper formulation of failure surfaces [3], [4]. Introducing an appropriate linearization of the yield conditions, considering associative flow rules between the strain rates and resistances, due to interlock between masonry blocks, a limit analysis problem is formulated as a Linear Programming mathematical problem.

In addition to the aforementioned rigid block model, 3-D beam elements can be associated to build realistic model assemblages. Such line elements are often used in masonry structures, such as wood and metal beams or tension bars. Aiming at developing a synthetic tool capable to handle different 3D failure mechanisms, the proposed model is implemented in Rhinoceros cad software [5]. In this context, a code

written in Python language is used to model the initial geometry and also to display the failure modes that result as solutions of the Linear Programming problem.

The church of St. Spyridonas of the castle of St. George on the Greek island of Cephalonia is being analyzed. The critical collapse mode is presented in the following Figure.

Analysis and Design and Optimization Using ScadaPro

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ABSTRACT

SCADA Pro is è software for Static & Dynamic analysis and design of advanced structures with 40 years of continuous research and development. Supports the design of new constructions as well as the assessment and redesign of existing ones and all structural materials (Concrete, Steel, Timber, Masonry, Composite Slabs) & Mixed Structures and contains Eurocodes and Saudi Building Code. Integrates BIM technology and offers two-way communication with CSI ETABS / SAP2000, AutoCAD and more other architectural and structural programs. Incorporates the OCP Technology (Optimization of Structures) for Cost Reduction. ACE-OCP is a computing platform that applies optimization theory to real structures with the ultimate goal of minimizing construction costs (Materials and labor).

1st International Conference on Optimization Driven Architectural Design

Jordan, November 5th - 7th, 2019

Program Outline

4/11	Welcome reception/registration stage with cocktail and sweet	21:00	
5/11 - 6/11 - 7/11	Registration	08:00-09:00	
	Inaugural Session	09:00-09:30	
	Keynote	Keynote talk: 1	09:30-10:00
		Keynote talk: 2	10:00-10:30
	Coffee break/ Networking	10:30-11:00	
	Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions	11:00-12:30	
	Lunch break / Networking	12:30-14:00	
	Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions	14:00-15:30	
	Coffee break/ Networking	15:30-16:00	
	Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions	16:00-17:30	
Dinner (6/11/2019)	20:00-24:00		
8/11	Visit Archeological places (Optional)	08:00-18:00	

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- ✓ Shape and topology optimization: topological derivatives, level set methods, isogeometry-based shape optimization, topometry and topography optimization, sensitivity analysis, etc.
- ✓ Linear, nonlinear, stochastic, parametric, discrete and dynamic programming – modelling.
- ✓ Optimization software.
- ✓ Evolutionary algorithms, swarm optimization, scatter search, etc.
- ✓ Parallel and distributed computing in optimization – Cloud computing, GPGPU computing environment.
- ✓ Theory of metaheuristics, landscape analysis, convergence, large neighborhoods, etc.
- ✓ Multiple criteria decision making and optimization.
- ✓ Local search, tabu search, simulated annealing, VNS, ILS, etc.
- ✓ Hybrid methods with metaheuristics, machine learning, game theory, mathematical programming, constraint programming, co-evolutionary, etc.
- ✓ Energy (energy harvesting, storage, delivery, efficiency, etc.), environment and climate.
- ✓ Artificial intelligence, surrogates-metamodels, fuzzy systems.
- ✓ Structural optimization: composite materials, transient loads and crash, fatigue and fracture, etc.
- ✓ Lifecycle design optimization and structural health monitoring.
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MONDAY 4.11.2019

18:00 20:00	Registration	Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)
21:00	Welcome reception/registration stage with cocktail and sweet	Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)

MONDAY 4.11

TUESDAY 5.11.2019

08:00 09:30	Registration	Rubi (B1 Floor)
09:30 10:00	Opening Ceremony	Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)

TUESDAY 5.11

10:00 10:30 Plenary Lectures

Section Chairs: *K. Abdalla, M.C. Phocas*

Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)

10:00 **Linear Programming in the Analysis and Design of Structures**
10:30 *V. K. Koumousis*

Coffee break/ Networking (10:30 – 11:00)

TUESDAY 5.11.2019

TUESDAY 5.11

11:00 12:30		Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions
Mini-Symposium (MS): Bioclimatic Building Design Improvement Through Performance Optimization Section Chairs: A. Kouvela, S. Inetzi		Fayrouz (B1 Floor)
11:00	Bioclimatic building design theory and application	
11:30	A. Couvelas (Keynote)	
11:30	Motion sequence optimization of a planar structure	
11:45	M. Matheou, I. Chamseddine, M Kokkolaras, M. C. Phocas	
11:45	Design optimization to enhance passive energy strategies. The KNOW HOWse project for Solar Decathlon Middle East 2018	
12:00	V. Belpoliti, M. Calzolari, P. Davoli, H. Altan, R. Nassif	
12:00	Comportment of wind flow of funnels incorporated in the “House of the Winds” designed by Agnes Couvelas	
12:15	S. Inetzi	
12:15	Optimization of a sail-shaped façade structure of a multi-storey office building	
12:30	F. Maden, E. Yıldırım, D. Ölmez, A. Couvelas	

Structural Optimization I		Yakut (B1 Floor)
Section Chairs: K.D. Tsavdaridis, R. Al-Rousan		
11:00	Control of vibrations of common pedestrian bridges in Jordan with tuned mass dampers	
11:30	M. Alhassan, R. Al-Rousan, S. Al-Khasawneh (Keynote)	
11:30	Method for designing optimal usable structures of computer system for its emergency reconfiguration	
11:45	S. Rozmus, A. W. Kozina	
11:45	Multi-axis 3D printing of material reduced shell structures on reconfigurable supporting system using topology optimization principles	
12:00	O. Kontovourkis, M. C. Phocas, G. Tryfonos, C. Georgiou	
12:00	The optimum reinforced concrete deck stiffness of cable-stayed bridge decks	
12:15	A. A. Alkhaldeh, R. Z. Al-Rousan	
12:15	Optimum configuration of CFRP composites for strengthening of reinforced concrete beams considering the contact constraint	
12:30	L. K. Amaireh, A. Al-Tamimi	

TUESDAY 5.11.2019

Sustainability Design I

Section Chairs: *M. Sandberg, F. Maden*

Diamond
Ballroom
(B2 Floor)

TUESDAY 5.11

11:00 11:30	Sustainability life-cycle evaluation of timber dwellings in north of Sweden based on environmental impact and optimization of energy and cost <i>J. Mukkavaara, M. Sandberg, K. Sandberg, A. Pousette, J. Norén (Keynote)</i>
11:30 11:45	Towards sustainable building design: the impact of architectural design features on cooling energy consumption and cost in Saudi Arabia <i>A. Al-Saggaf, M. Taha, T. Hegazy, H. Ahmed</i>
11:45 12:00	Design and creation of an energy efficient prefabricated housing unit based on specific taxonomy and optimization techniques <i>A. G. Michael, A. L. Savvides, A. F. Triantafyllidou, C. G. Vassiliades</i>
12:00 12:15	Assessment of daylight performance and impact of shading devices for typical in-patient rooms in healthcare facilities in Cyprus <i>M. Englezou, A. G. Michael</i>
12:15 12:30	Optimization based feasibility study for filler slabs as a response towards the ECBC roof compliance with respect to thermal transmittance <i>R. R. Acharya, P. Kishore, M. Raghuprem, P. G. Kini, S. Shetty, A. Raj</i>

Lunch break / Networking (12:30 – 14:00)

14:00 15:30

Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions

Structural Optimization II

Section Chairs: *Ch. J. Gantes, Y. Al-Smadi*

Yakut
(B1 Floor)

14:00 14:30	Resonance investigation and its effects on weight optimization of tubular steel wind turbine towers <i>K. G. Koulatsou, G. Kazakis, Ch. J. Gantes, N. D. Lagaros (Keynote)</i>
14:30 14:45	Weight and material optimization of scissor-hinge structures according to the various span lengths <i>Y. Akgün, F. Maden, E. Yildirim</i>
14:45 15:00	Some structural design issues on a timber bridge for pedestrians <i>M. A. Liuzzi, A. Fiore, R. Greco</i>
15:00 15:15	Thinking outside the box: small diameter sheaves replacing big sheave for vertical lift bridge <i>Y. M. Al-Smadi</i>
15:15 15:30	Parametric investigation for the improvement of the overall sustainable performance of an innovative masonry wall system <i>A. Kyriakidis, R. Illampas, A. Michael</i>

1st International Conference on Optimization - Driven Architectural Design

November 5th – 7th, 2019, Amman, Jordan

TUESDAY 5.11.2019

TUESDAY 5.11

Sustainability Design II		Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)
Section Chairs: <i>F. Maden, A. Couvelas</i>		
14:00 14:30	Multi criteria evaluation for sustainable urban growth in an-nuayyimah, jordan; post war study <i>A. A. Gharaibeh, A. H. Shaamal, M. H. Ali (Keynote)</i>	
14:30 11:45	The impact of installing a concave curved profile blind to a glass window on visual comfort in office buildings <i>E. F. Triantafyllidou, A. G. Michael</i>	
14:45 15:00	The framework for assessing similarity measures impact on classification confidence based on probabilistic record linkage model <i>M. Mazurek, K. Mierzejewski</i>	
15:00 15:15	Optimization of daylighting and energy performance in hot - arid climate <i>J. Awad, L. Abd-Rabo</i>	
15:15 15:30	Optimization based feasibility analysis for energy conservation building code (ECBC) compliance of opaque wall assemblies in different climatic zones of India <i>P. Kishore, P. G. Kini, A. Raj</i>	

Coffee break/ Networking (15:30 – 16:00)

16:00 17:30	Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions	
Sustainability Design III		Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)
Section Chairs: <i>A. Gharaibeh, A. Couvelas</i>		
16:00 16:15	A modified semi-probabilistic approach for the assessment of the residual service life of concrete structures subjected to carbonation <i>Z. A. Ebrahim, Y. A. Abdel-jawad</i>	
16:15 16:30	Dynamic façade design based on visual comfort and daylight performance optimization <i>M. Uncu, F. Maden, D. Ölmez</i>	
16:30 16:45	Optimization of public spaces through network potentials of communities <i>M. Androulaki, E. Frangedaki, P. Antoniadis</i>	
16:45 17:00	Optimization practice of water resources for the needs of the local communities in mainland Greece (case study of Karies Peloponnese) <i>G.-F. Sargentis, P. Dimitriadis, R. Ioannidis, T. Iliopoulou, E. Frangedaki, D. Koutsoyiannis</i>	

TUESDAY 5.11.2019

Structural Optimization III Section Chairs: <i>M. Issa, N. Kallioras</i>		Yakut (B1 Floor)
16:00 16:30	A review on optimal design of large-scale suspended-dome using meta heuristic method <i>M. Rezaei, M. Issa (Keynote)</i>	
16:30 16:45	Structural optimization of elastic circular arches and design criteria <i>F. Trentadue, A. Fiore, R. Greco, G. C. Marano, G. De Marco, B. Briseghella, N. D. Lagaros</i>	
16:45 17:00	Structural Optimization Computing Platform (SOCP) and SCIA Software <i>Ch.Ch. Mitropoulou, G. Kazakis, S. Sotiropoulos, N.D. Lagaros, N. Ath. Kallioras</i>	
17:00 17:15	DzAI N: Deep learning based generative design <i>N. Ath. Kallioras, N. D. Lagaros</i>	
17:15 17:30	Carbon nanotubes dosage optimization for strength enhancement of cementitious composites <i>M. R. Irshidat, Nasser Al-Nuaimi, Soheb Salim, Mohamed Rabie</i>	
17:30 17:45	On the performance of differential evolution variants in constrained structural optimization <i>M. Georgioudakis, V. Plevris</i>	

TUESDAY 5.11

WEDNESDAY 6.11.2019

09:30 10:30	Plenary Lectures	
Section Chairs: <i>G.C. Marano, N.D. Lagaros</i>		Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)
09:30 10:00	Dome Space Frames Optimization Using three Meta-Heuristic Algorithms <i>M. Issa, M. Rezaei</i>	
10:00 10:30	Dynamic response of RC bridge span subjected to blast wave shock <i>Y. M. Al-Smadi</i>	

WEDNESDAY 6.11

Coffee break/ Networking (10:30 – 11:00)

WEDNESDAY 6.11.2019

WEDNESDAY 6.11

11:00 12:30 Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions

BIM Workshop: Towards Effective BIM Adoption and Digital Transformation; Potential, Challenges and the way forward
Section Chairs: *Issam El-Absi*

Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)

**11:00
12:30**

BIM Workshop by CCC:

Towards effective BIM adoption and digital transformation; potential, challenges and the way forward II

Antiseismic Design II
Section Chairs: *M. Alhassan, R. Al-Rousan*

Yakut (B1 Floor)

**11:00
11:30** Shape optimization of assembled single-layer grid structure with semi-rigid joints
F. LIU, K. D. Tsavdaridis (Keynote)

**11:30
12:00** Integrating Model Simulations and Smart Sensing for the Coupled Transport-Degradation Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Structures
A. N. Ababneh, H. Hamidane, Y. Wang, M. Abdelrahman, Y. Xi (Keynote)

**12:00
12:15** Optimal design criteria for seismic retrofitting of RC columns with steel jacketing technique
M. Malavisi, F. Di Trapani, G. C. Marano, A. Fiore, R. Greco

**12:15
12:30** Optimizing the impact of detergents contamination on the geotechnical properties of soils
A. A. Sharo, B. H. Daradkabh

WEDNESDAY 6.11.2019

Applications I Section Chairs: <i>T. Nowicki, A. Rhiat</i>		Fayrouz (B1 Floor)
11:00 11:30	Modeling and characteristics investigation of warehouse business processes in a clothes clean & rental company <i>T. Nowicki, R. Waszkowski (Keynote)</i>	
11:30 11:45	Combining mobile robotics and packing for optimal deliveries <i>A. Aggoun, A. Rhiat, R. Lachere</i>	
11:45 12:00	Optimization of deployment architecture in SOA systems <i>A. P. Woźniak</i>	
12:00 12:15	Efficiency investigation and optimization of contract management business processes in a workwear rental and laundry service company <i>R. Waszkowski, T. Nowicki</i>	
12:15 12:30	Fixed charge minimum cost network flow approach to optimize product assembly <i>S. Burggraeve, P. Lietaert, J. Goos, A. Rosich</i>	

WEDNESDAY 6.11

Lunch break / Networking (12:30 – 14:00)

14:00 15:30		Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions
Arches Design Section Chairs: <i>G. Marano, R. Greco</i>		Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)
14:00 14:30	Optimal pre-stressed arches shapes with variable section subject to vertical live loads and self-weight <i>V. Debiagi, B. Chiaia, G. C. Marano, A. Fiore, R. Greco, L. Sardone, R. Cucuzza, G.L. Cascella, M. Spinelli, N.D. Lagaros (Keynote)</i>	
14:30 14:45	A case study on the selection of optimum loop units for the deployable arc structures exposed to lateral and non-uniform gravity loads <i>K. Yüçetürk, E. Aktaş, F. Maden, Ş. Gur, Ch. Ch Mitropoulou</i>	
14:45 15:00	Volume optimization of perfectly-constrained arches <i>F. Trentadue, G. C. Marano, A. Fiore, R. Greco, G.L. Cascella, M. Spinelli, N. D. Lagaros</i>	
15:00 15:15	Optimal circular arch shapes under multiple load conditions <i>L. Sardone, F. Trentadue, A. Fiore, R. Greco, R. Cucuzza, G.L. Cascella, M. Spinelli, N. D. Lagaros</i>	
15:15 15:30	Semi-analytical solution of in-plane vibrations of circular arches <i>A. Babahammou, R. Benamar</i>	

WEDNESDAY 6.11.2019

WEDNESDAY 6.11

Antiseismic Design I Section Chairs: <i>A. Athanatopoulou, M. Alhassan</i>		Yakut (B1 Floor)
14:00 14:30	Parametric analyses for the evaluation of soil-structure interaction effects on eigenfrequencies and damping ratios <i>V. G. Terzi, A. Athanatopoulou (Keynote)</i>	
14:30 15:00	Optimizing the use of formalin aqueous by using disposed formalin aqueous to improve properties of expansive soil <i>A. A. Sharo, M. O. Taamneh (Keynote)</i>	
15:00 15:30	Analysis and design and optimization using ScadaPro <i>A. Bagourdi-Degkleri, K. Abdalla, K. Abdalla (Keynote)</i>	

Applications II Section Chairs: <i>M. Chmielewski, N. Kallioras</i>		Fayrouz (B1 Floor)
14:00 14:15	Methods and analytical tools for assessing tactical situation in military operations using potential approach and sensor data fusion <i>M. Chmielewski, M. Kukielka, P. Pieczonka, T. Gutowski (Keynote)</i>	
14:15 14:30	Risk based approach in scope of cyber security threats and requirements <i>J. Napiórkowski, J. Stanik, T. Protasowicki, R. Hoffman</i>	
14:30 14:45	Analytical tools for evaluation pharmaceutical treatment of neurological diseases – a case study <i>M. Chmielewski, M. Kukielka, P. Pieczonka, T. Gutowski</i>	
14:45 15:00	The importance of the integrated security system for critical infrastructure operation and safety <i>T. Protasowicki, J. Stanik, J. Napiórkowski, R. Hoffmann</i>	
15:00 15:15	Diagrid systems coupled with closed- and open-section shear walls: Optimization of geometrical characteristics in tall buildings <i>G. Lacidogna, G. Nitti, D. Scaramozzino, A. Carpinteri</i>	
15:15 15:30	Architectural and Structural Optimization Research of Structural Forms Topologically Transformed <i>A. Nowak</i>	

Coffee break/ Networking (15:30 – 16:00)

Conference Banquet (20:00 – 24:00)

Thursday 7.11.2019

Coffee break/ Networking (10:30 – 11:00)

Thursday 7.11

11:00 12:30 Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions

Topology Optimization I
Section Chairs: R. Estevez, D.C. Charnpis
Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)

11:00 11:30	Topology optimization in acoustics and elasto-acoustics via a level-set method <i>R. Estevez, J. Desai, A. Faure, G. Michailidis (Keynote)</i>
11:30 12:00	Coupling shear walls with connecting beams: an investigation based on topology optimization <i>D. C. Charnpis (Keynote)</i>
12:00 12:15	Evaluation of optimal lateral resisting systems for tall buildings subject to horizontal loads <i>G. Angelucci, O. AlShawa, F. Mollaioli</i>
12:15 12:30	DL-Scale: Deep learning for model upgrading in topology optimization <i>N. Ath. Kallioras, N. D. Lagaros</i>

Architectural Design I
Section Chairs: V. Belpoliti, E. Frangedaki
Yakut (B1 Floor)

11:00 11:30	Shaping the microclimate. CFD-assisted design optimization to enhance the outdoor comfort of a recreational complex in the UAE <i>V. Belpoliti, H. Altan, H. Alsebai, O. Melahfci (Keynote)</i>
11:30 11:45	Adaptable emergency shelter: a case study in generative design and additive manufacturing in mass customization era <i>S. Salta, N. Papavasileiou, K. Pylotis, M. Katsaros</i>
11:45 12:00	Forms follows brain functions: a computational mapping approach <i>M. Christofi, M. Katsaros</i>
12:00 12:30	Transformable building envelope design in architectural education <i>M. Matheou, A. Couvelas, M. C. Phocas (Keynote)</i>

Thursday 7.11.2019

Machine Learning		Fayrouz (B1 Floor)
Section Chairs: Z. Tarapata, M. Alhassan		
11:00 11:30	Data-driven machine learning system for optimization of processes supporting the distribution of goods and services – a case study <i>Z. Tarapata, T. Nowicki, R. Antkiewicz, J. Dudziński, K. Janik (Keynote)</i>	
11:30 11:45	Optimization of bus stops locations using GIS techniques and artificial intelligence <i>N. Shatnawi, A. A. Al-Omari, H. Al-Qudah</i>	
11:45 12:00	A new model for predicting the transfer length of prestressing strands optimized using artificial neural networks <i>M. Alhassan, A. Ababneh, N. Betoush</i>	
12:00 12:15	Best of both worlds – using computational design and deep learning for real-time urban performance evaluation <i>T. Galanos, A. Chronis, O. Vesely, A. Aichinger, R. Koenig</i>	
12:15 12:30	Virtual reality-neural networks for reconstruction of devastated cities by earthquakes: lacustrine deposits in Mexico City <i>S. R. Garcia, P. A. Trejo, A. García</i>	

Thursday 7.11

Lunch break / Networking (12:30 – 14:00)

14:00	15:30	Oral Presentations and Panel Discussions
Topology Optimization II and Risk Management		Diamond Ballroom (B2 Floor)
Section Chairs: N. Kallioras, R. Al-Rousan		
14:00 14:15	Topology optimization of framed structures using SAP2000 <i>S. Sotiropoulos, N. D. Lagaros (Keynote)</i>	
14:15 14:30	High performance topology optimization computing platform <i>S. Sotiropoulos, N. D. Lagaros</i>	
14:30 14:45	Two-scale topology optimization using homogenization theory <i>K. Ipsiladis, G. Kazakis, N.D. Lagaros</i>	
14:45 15:00	Measurement models of information security based on the principles and practices for risk-based approach <i>J. Stanik, J. Napiórkowski, T. Protasowicki, R. Hoffmann</i>	
15:00 15:15	Models and methods for measurement of risk management system usability <i>R. Hoffmann, J. Stanik, T. Protasowicki, J. Napiórkowski</i>	
15:15 15:30	Mathematical models of information operations <i>R. Kasprzyk</i>	

Thursday 7.11.2019

Thursday 7.11

Architectural Design II		Yakut (B1 Floor)
Section Chairs: A. Fiore, E. Frangedaki		
14:00 14:30	Optimizing stages of restoration of Fujian Tulou through participatory design and collective practices <i>E. Frangedaki, X. Gao, N.D. Lagaros (Keynote)</i>	
14:30 15:00	Optimal design criteria for form finding of double curved surfaces <i>C. Sulpizio, A. Fiore, I. Vanzi, B. Briseghella (Keynote)</i>	
15:00 15:15	Computer-aided approach to public buildings floor plan generation. Generator. <i>E. Gavrilov, M. Dennemark, S. Schneider, R. Koenig</i>	
15:15 15:30	Typology-based generation of multi-family-residential buildings <i>I. Osintseva, A. Berst, M. Bielik, R. Koenig, S. Schneider</i>	

Sustainability Design IV		Fayrouz (B1 Floor)
Section Chairs: F.A. Abdulla, R. Hatamleh		
14:00 14:15	Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) based optimum wall with respect to Thermal transmittance and thickness composition for different commercial pockets of tier 1 city in temperate climatic zone of India <i>S. Shetty, P. Kishore, P. Kini, R. R. Acharya, A. Raj</i>	
14:15 14:30	Genetic algorithm for embodied energy optimization of steel-concrete composite beams <i>A.H. Whitworth, K.D. Tsavdaridis</i>	
14:30 14:45	Enhancement of the mechanical properties of kaolin geopolymer using sodium hydroxide and calcium oxide <i>F. Matalkah, R. Aqel, A. Ababneh</i>	
14:45 15:00	Water Resources Management in Amman/Zarqa Basin (Al-Corridor Well Field) <i>R. Hatamleh, M. Shawaqfah, I. Alqadah, A. Adaileh</i>	
15:00 15:15	Rainfall-Runoff modeling for Semi-arid and trans-boundary Yarmouk River Basin <i>F. A. Abdull, A. W. Al-Shurafat</i>	
15:15 15:30	Assessment of the impact of potential climate change on the surface water of a trans-boundary basin: case study Yarmouk River <i>F. A. Abdulla, A. W. Al-Shurafat</i>	

Coffee break/ Networking (15:30 – 16:00)

Thursday 7.11.2019

Closing Discussion

Section Chairs: *K. Abdalla, M.C. Phocas, G.C. Marano*

**Diamond
Ballroom
(B2 Floor)**

**16:00
17:30**

Closing Discussion

Thursday 7.11